

Úloha opakování vět a její souvislost s výsledky paměťových a jazykových testů

2022-10-07

Příprava dat

Výpočet a-prime pro výsledky TVJT

```
data_aprime <- read_excel("Příloha 9_Dataset k výpočtu aprime v úloze posuzování pravdivosti vět.xlsx", sheet=1)
aprime.stats_all <- psycho::dprime(n_hit=data_aprime$hit_all,n_fa=data_aprime$FalseAlarm_all,
n_targets = 16, n_distractors = 16, adjusted = FALSE)
data_aprime$a_prime_all <- aprime.stats_all$aprime
```

Soubor summary

```
data_sum <- read_excel("Příloha 10_Dataset k sumarizačním analýzám.xlsx", sheet=1)
data_sum$group <- relevel(factor(data_sum$group), "TD")
data_sum$vocab_centered <- scale(data_sum$vocab,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_sum$forward_DS_centered <- scale(data_sum$forward_DS,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_sum$backward_DS_centered <- scale(data_sum$backward_DS,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_sum$NR_centered <- scale(data_sum$NR,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_sum$LS_seq_centered <- scale(data_sum$LS_seq,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_sum$LS_item_centered <- scale(data_sum$LS_item,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_sum_VD <- subset(data_sum, group=="DLD")
data_sum_TJV <- subset(data_sum, group=="TD")
```

Opakování vět

```
data_SI <- read_excel("Příloha 11_Dataset k úloze opakování vět.xlsx", sheet=1)
data_SI <- data_SI %>% mutate(group = group %>% fct_relevel("TD","DLD"))
data_SI$group %>% levels()
```

```
## [1] "TD" "DLD"
```

```
data_SI$TargConstr <- factor(data_SI$TargConstr)
data_SI$Constr <- factor(data_SI$Constr)
data_SI$num_changes <- ordered(data_SI$num_changes)
data_SI$gram_sent <- as.numeric(data_SI$gram_sent)
data_SI$use_struct_binom <- as.numeric(data_SI$use_struct_binom)
data_SI$gram_in_core_binom <- as.numeric(data_SI$gram_in_core_binom)
data_SI$vocab <- scale(data_SI$vocab,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_SI$forward_DS <- scale(data_SI$forward_DS,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_SI$backward_DS <- scale(data_SI$backward_DS,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_SI$NR <- scale(data_SI$NR,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_SI$LS_seq <- scale(data_SI$LS_seq,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_SI$LS_item <- scale(data_SI$LS_item,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_SI$EP_all <- scale(data_SI$EP_all,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_SI$EP_adj <- scale(data_SI$EP_adj,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_SI$EP_rightRCs <- scale(data_SI$EP_rightRCs,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
str(data_SI)
```

```

## tibble [6,046 × 45] (S3: tbl_df/tbl/data.frame)
## $ child      : chr [1:6046] "B_D4" "B_D4" "B_D4" "B_D4" ...
## $ gender    : chr [1:6046] "F" "F" "F" "F" ...
## $ group     : Factor w/ 2 levels "TD","DLD": 2 2 2 2 2 2 2 2 2 ...
## $ age       : num [1:6046] 88 88 88 88 88 88 88 88 88 ...
## $ age_centered : num [1:6046] -6.4 -6.4 -6.4 -6.4 -6.4 ...
## $ item      : num [1:6046] 26 1 18 10 6 22 12 3 19 17 ...
## $ TargConstr : Factor w/ 3 levels "AdjPhr","CenterEmb",...: 1 2 3 2 1 3 3 1 3 3
...
## $ Constr    : Factor w/ 2 levels "AdjPhr","RelClPhr": 1 2 2 2 1 2 2 1 2 2 ...
## $ HeadRelCl : chr [1:6046] NA "Subj" "Obj" "Obj" ...
## $ TargForm  : chr [1:6046] "4SGF" "1SGMA" "2SGF" "4SGMA" ...
## $ TargCase  : chr [1:6046] "4SGF" "1SGM" "2SGF" "4SGM" ...
## $ TargEnd   : chr [1:6046] "ou" "ý/ej" "é/ý" "ého/ýho" ...
## $ TargSent  : chr [1:6046] "O červenou růži si poranila Růženka prst." "Táta,
který jezdil traktorem, vozil obilí." "Doktor si ošetřil ruku, do které se uhodil." "Osla, ve
kterého se změnil princ, políbila víla." ...
## $ 1_repetition : chr [1:6046] "O růži, která prst." "Táta vezl traktorem, který
byl obilí." "Doktor si ošetřil ruku, jak si uhodil." "Políbil princ." ...
## $ 2_repetition : chr [1:6046] " " NA NA "Ve kterém políbil princ, ve kterém byla
víla." ...
## $ 3_repetition : chr [1:6046] " " NA NA NA ...
## $ num_repetition : num [1:6046] 1 1 1 2 1 1 1 1 1 1 ...
## $ changes      : chr [1:6046] " " "Táta, 3který 2jezdil traktorem, 2vozil obil
í." "Doktor si ošetřil ruku, 0do 2které 2se uhodil." NA ...
## $ num_changes  : Ord.factor w/ 6 levels "0"<"1"<"2"<"3"<...: 6 4 4 6 6 6 6 6 4 3
...
## $ gram_sent    : num [1:6046] 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 ...
## $ degree_confidence_sent: num [1:6046] 1 1 2 1 1 2 1 1 2 1 ...
## $ use_struct   : chr [1:6046] "OtherOmit" "AnotherWhStruct" "TargWhStruct" "Anot
herWhStruct" ...
## $ use_struct_detail : chr [1:6046] "OmitVerb" "RightBranch" "TargWhStruct" "RightBran
ch" ...
## $ attached_structure : chr [1:6046] NA NA NA NA ...
## $ use_struct_binom  : num [1:6046] 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ...
## $ use_TargHead     : chr [1:6046] "6SGF" "7SGMI" "TargHead" "1SGMA" ...
## $ use_TargWord     : chr [1:6046] "wh-word" "který" "jak" "který" ...
## $ use_TargCase     : chr [1:6046] "1SGF" "1SGMI" "4SGF" "6SGMA" ...
## $ use_TargCase_binom : num [1:6046] NA 0 NA 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 ...
## $ gram_in_core     : chr [1:6046] "gram_NP" "gram" "gram" "gram" ...
## $ gram_in_core_binom : num [1:6046] NA 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 ...
## $ degree_confidence_core: num [1:6046] 1 1 1 2 1 2 1 1 2 1 ...
## $ notes           : chr [1:6046] "OmitPrep" NA "0resump_4SG" NA ...
## $ vocab           : num [1:6046, 1] -5.45 -5.45 -5.45 -5.45 -5.45 ...
## ..- attr(*, "scaled:center")= num 32.4
## $ forward_DS      : num [1:6046, 1] -0.103 -0.103 -0.103 -0.103 -0.103 ...
## ..- attr(*, "scaled:center")= num 5.1
## $ backward_DS     : num [1:6046, 1] 2.17 2.17 2.17 2.17 2.17 ...
## ..- attr(*, "scaled:center")= num 1.83
## $ NR              : num [1:6046, 1] 1.91 1.91 1.91 1.91 1.91 ...
## ..- attr(*, "scaled:center")= num 17.1
## $ LS_seq          : num [1:6046, 1] -0.0875 -0.0875 -0.0875 -0.0875 -0.0875 ...
## ..- attr(*, "scaled:center")= num 2.09
## $ LS_item         : num [1:6046, 1] -0.415 -0.415 -0.415 -0.415 -0.415 ...
## ..- attr(*, "scaled:center")= num 9.41

```

```
## $ TVJT_all : num [1:6046] 0.296 0.296 0.296 0.296 0.296 ...
## $ TVJT_adj : num [1:6046] 0.375 0.375 0.375 0.375 0.375 0.375 0.375 0.375 0.375 0.375 ...
## $ TVJT_embRCs : num [1:6046] 0.188 0.188 0.188 0.188 0.188 ...
## $ EP_all : num [1:6046, 1] -21.5 -21.5 -21.5 -21.5 -21.5 ...
## ..- attr(*, "scaled:center")= num 44.5
## $ EP_adj : num [1:6046, 1] -14.5 -14.5 -14.5 -14.5 -14.5 ...
## ..- attr(*, "scaled:center")= num 28.5
## $ EP_rightRCs : num [1:6046, 1] -7.03 -7.03 -7.03 -7.03 -7.03 ...
## ..- attr(*, "scaled:center")= num 16
```

```
data_SI_AdjPhr <- subset(data_SI, Constr=="AdjPhr")
data_SI_RelClPhr <- subset(data_SI, Constr=="RelClPhr")
data_SI_core <- subset(data_SI, degree_confidence_core=="1"|degree_confidence_core=="2")
data_SI_RelClPhr_core <- subset(data_SI_core, Constr=="RelClPhr")
```

Elicitovaná produkce

```
data_EP_all <- read_excel("Příloha 12_Dataset k úloze elicítované produkce.xlsx", sheet = 1)
data_EP_all <- subset(data_EP_all, degree_of_confidence=="1"|degree_of_confidence=="2") # Not Answer bez degree of confidence => nepočítá se
data_EP_all <- data_EP_all %>% mutate(group = group %>% fct_relevel("TD","DLD"))
data_EP_all$group %>% levels()
```

```
## [1] "TD" "DLD"
```

```
data_EP_all$Constr <- factor(data_EP_all$Constr)
data_EP_all$score_total <- ordered(data_EP_all$score_total)
data_EP_all$use_struct_binom <- as.numeric(data_EP_all$use_struct_binom)
data_EP_all$gram_in_core_binom <- as.numeric(data_EP_all$gram_in_core_binom)
data_EP_all$TargCase <- factor(data_EP_all$TargCase)
data_EP_AdjPhr <- subset(data_EP_all, Constr=="AdjPhr")
data_EP_RelClPhr <- subset(data_EP_all, Constr=="RelClPhr")
```

Posuzování pravdivosti vět

Accuracy = přesnost odpovědi (1 = dítě řeklo cílovou odpověď - tj. "ANO", pokud bylo cílovou odpovědí "ANO" a "NE", pokud bylo cílovou odpovědí "NE"; 0 = dítě neřeklo cílovou odpověď). TargAnswer = cílová odpověď (1 = ANO, 0 = NE).

```
data_TVJT <- read_excel("Příloha 13_Dataset k úloze posuzování pravdivosti vět.xlsx", sheet = 1)
data_TVJT <- data_TVJT %>% mutate(group = group %>% fct_relevel("TD","DLD"))
data_TVJT$group %>% levels()
```

```
## [1] "TD" "DLD"
```

```
data_TVJT$Constr <- factor(data_TVJT$Constr)
data_TVJT$vocab <- scale(data_TVJT$vocab,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_TVJT$forward_DS <- scale(data_TVJT$forward_DS,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_TVJT$backward_DS <- scale(data_TVJT$backward_DS,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_TVJT$NR <- scale(data_TVJT$NR,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_TVJT$LS_seq <- scale(data_TVJT$LS_seq,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
data_TVJT$LS_item <- scale(data_TVJT$LS_item,center = TRUE, scale = FALSE)
```

Participanti

t-test - rozdíl mezi skupinami ve slovní zásobě na základě skóru

```
DLD <- c(27,47,27,43,44,42,40,41,45,38,18,47,46,38,39,40,16,15,20,9,32,23,36,38,21,45,40,39,21,29,32,47,24,25,29,41,38,17,27,15,20,17,14,48,28,41,43,36,14,24,25,34,17,34,46,51,42,38,52,39,18,18,36)
mean(DLD)
```

```
## [1] 32.31746
```

```
sd(DLD)
```

```
## [1] 11.38735
```

```
TD <- c(20,32,24,14,41,22,39,10,26,34,37,38,46,22,55,44,43,16,49,50,38,40,23,24,42,43,19,34,11,14,15,26,31,34,50,38,44,13,38,37,42,23,16,36,11,29,22,31,41,41,33,32,48,39,23,37,26,45,33,43,45,36,45)
mean(TD)
```

```
## [1] 32.5873
```

```
sd(TD)
```

```
## [1] 11.50264
```

```
var.test(x = DLD, y = TD, conf.level = 0.95)
```

```
##  
## F test to compare two variances  
##  
## data: DLD and TD  
## F = 0.98005, num df = 62, denom df = 62, p-value = 0.937  
## alternative hypothesis: true ratio of variances is not equal to 1  
## 95 percent confidence interval:  
## 0.5929858 1.6197803  
## sample estimates:  
## ratio of variances  
## 0.9800544
```

```
t.test(x = DLD, y = TD, paired = FALSE, var.equal = TRUE, conf.level = 0.95)
```

```
##  
## Two Sample t-test  
##  
## data: DLD and TD  
## t = -0.13233, df = 124, p-value = 0.8949  
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0  
## 95 percent confidence interval:  
## -4.306046 3.766364  
## sample estimates:  
## mean of x mean of y  
## 32.31746 32.58730
```

Charakteristika jazykových a paměťových schopností ve skupině dětí s VD a s TJV

Opakování vět

```
summary(errors_group_age_Constr <- c1mm(num_changes ~ group+Constr+age_centered + (1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item), data=data_SI))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: num_changes ~ group + Constr + age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) +
## (1 + group | item)
## data: data_SI
##
## link threshold nobs logLik AIC niter max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 5941 -7688.89 15405.78 2724(19531) 4.09e-03 2.6e+03
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept) 2.2369 1.4956
## ConstrRelClPhr 0.1055 0.3248 0.315
## item (Intercept) 1.1579 1.0761
## groupDLD 0.1053 0.3244 -0.458
## Number of groups: child 126, item 48
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD 1.73553 0.28670 6.054 1.42e-09 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr 1.30565 0.31054 4.204 2.62e-05 ***
## age_centered -0.05622 0.01526 -3.685 0.000229 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
## Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1 -1.9497 0.3293 -5.921
## 1|2 -0.6260 0.3275 -1.911
## 2|3 0.4940 0.3273 1.509
## 3|4 1.5313 0.3278 4.671
## 4|5 2.5461 0.3289 7.742
## (105 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
summary(errors_group_age_Constr_separ_int <- cldmm(num_changes ~ group*Constr+group*age_centere
d+Constr*age_centered + (1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),data=data_SI))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: num_changes ~ group * Constr + group * age_centered + Constr *
##   age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
## data:   data_SI
##
## link threshold nobs logLik  AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible  5941 -7687.91 15409.82 3981(34433) 1.26e+00 1.4e+04
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    2.1799  1.4765
##   ConstrRelClPhr  0.1062  0.3258  0.345
## item (Intercept)     1.1534  1.0740
##   groupDLD         0.1076  0.3280 -0.462
## Number of groups:  child 126,  item 48
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD          1.64736    0.28919   5.696 1.22e-08 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    1.21227    0.34036   3.562 0.000368 ***
## age_centered     -0.07340    0.02072  -3.542 0.000398 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr  0.03206    0.15951   0.201 0.840709
## groupDLD:age_centered  0.03817    0.03020   1.264 0.206265
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.00477    0.00679  -0.702 0.482389
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -2.0570    0.3352  -6.136
## 1|2  -0.7346    0.3335  -2.203
## 2|3   0.3842    0.3333   1.153
## 3|4   1.4208    0.3337   4.258
## 4|5   2.4353    0.3345   7.280
## (105 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
summary(errors_group_age_Constr_int <- clmm(num_changes ~ group*Constr*age_centered + (1+Constr
r|child)+(1+group|item),data=data_SI))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: num_changes ~ group * Constr * age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) +
##          (1 + group | item)
## data:    data_SI
##
## link threshold nobs logLik  AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 5941 -7687.48 15410.96 3824(36102) 1.22e-02 2.1e+04
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    2.1980   1.4826
##          ConstrRelClPhr 0.1009   0.3176  0.356
## item (Intercept)     1.1584   1.0763
##          groupDLD      0.1053   0.3245  -0.460
## Number of groups:  child 126,  item 48
##
## Coefficients:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD          1.7289108  0.3012482  5.739 9.51e-09 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    1.3014026  0.3458216  3.763 0.000168 ***
## age_centered      -0.0742479  0.0208087 -3.568 0.000360 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 0.0127564  0.1587823  0.080 0.935968
## groupDLD:age_centered 0.0398010  0.0302748  1.315 0.188625
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered 0.0004103  0.0102731  0.040 0.968138
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.0114271  0.0142811 -0.800 0.423622
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -1.9520   0.3710  -5.262
## 1|2  -0.6287   0.3697  -1.700
## 2|3   0.4911   0.3694   1.329
## 3|4   1.5283   0.3695   4.136
## 4|5   2.5431   0.3700   6.873
## (105 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
anova(errors_group_age_Constr,errors_group_age_Constr_separ_int,errors_group_age_Constr_int)
```

```
## Likelihood ratio tests of cumulative link models:
##
##                               formula:
## errors_group_age_Constr      num_changes ~ group + Constr + age_centered + (1 + Constr
r | child) + (1 + group | item)
## errors_group_age_Constr_separ_int num_changes ~ group * Constr + group * age_centered + Co
nstr * age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
## errors_group_age_Constr_int   num_changes ~ group * Constr * age_centered + (1 + Constr
r | child) + (1 + group | item)
##                               link: threshold:
## errors_group_age_Constr      logit flexible
## errors_group_age_Constr_separ_int logit flexible
## errors_group_age_Constr_int   logit flexible
##
##                               no.par   AIC   logLik LR.stat df Pr(>Chisq)
## errors_group_age_Constr        14 15406 -7688.9
## errors_group_age_Constr_separ_int 17 15410 -7687.9 1.9579 3 0.5812
## errors_group_age_Constr_int     18 15411 -7687.5 0.8626 1 0.3530
```

```
print(Anova.errors_group_age_Constr <- Anova.clm(errors_group_age_Constr,type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II tests)
##
## Response: num_changes
##           LR Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group           32.576  1 1.146e-08 ***
## Constr           15.172  1 9.814e-05 ***
## age_centered     12.976  1 0.0003156 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Posuzování pravdivosti vět

```
summary(TVJT_group_constr_age_TargAnswer <- glm(Accuracy~group+Constr+age_centered+TargAnsw
er+(1+TargAnswer|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_TVJT))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: Accuracy ~ group + Constr + age_centered + TargAnswer + (1 +
## TargAnswer | child) + (1 | item)
## Data: data_TVJT
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 4391.2  4447.9 -2186.6  4373.2    4023
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -4.2724 -0.6890  0.3218  0.6069  3.1654
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept) 0.6603   0.8126
## TargAnswer 2.6464   1.6268  -0.84
## item (Intercept) 0.4163   0.6452
## Number of obs: 4032, groups: child, 125; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)   0.33034   0.22669   1.457   0.145
## groupDLD     -0.53392   0.11155  -4.786 1.70e-06 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -0.39266   0.24138  -1.627   0.104
## age_centered  0.02468   0.00601   4.106 4.02e-05 ***
## TargAnswer    1.78729   0.28414   6.290 3.17e-10 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt
## groupDLD     -0.245
## CnstrRlClPh -0.532  0.004
## age_centerd -0.001 -0.016 -0.003
## TargAnswer  -0.574 -0.019 -0.006  0.015
```

```
summary(TVJT_Constr_age_int_group_TargAnswer <- glmer(Accuracy~age_centered*Constr+group+Targ
Answer+(1+TargAnswer|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_TVJT))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: Accuracy ~ age_centered * Constr + group + TargAnswer + (1 +
## TargAnswer | child) + (1 | item)
## Data: data_TVJT
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##  4385.8  4448.8  -2182.9  4365.8    4022
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -4.5575 -0.6829  0.3190  0.6120  2.9334
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)  0.6610    0.8130
##      TargAnswer    2.6405    1.6250  -0.84
## item (Intercept)  0.4153    0.6444
## Number of obs: 4032, groups: child, 125; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.332759   0.226607   1.468  0.14198
## age_centered      0.036327   0.007384   4.920 8.66e-07 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -0.394156   0.241178  -1.634  0.10220
## groupDLD         -0.535067   0.111787  -4.786 1.70e-06 ***
## TargAnswer        1.790484   0.283896   6.307 2.85e-10 ***
## age_centered:ConstrRelClPhr -0.022703   0.008252  -2.751  0.00593 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) ag_cnt CnsRCP grpDLD TrgAns
## age_centerd  0.004
## CnstrRlClPh -0.532 -0.009
## groupDLD    -0.245 -0.018  0.004
## TargAnswer  -0.573  0.017 -0.006 -0.019
## ag_cnt:CRCP -0.005 -0.578  0.004  0.008 -0.008
```

```
summary(TVJT_group_constr_int_group_age_int_Constr_age_int_TargAnswer <- glmer(Accuracy~group
*Constr+group*age_centered+age_centered*Constr+TargAnswer+(1+TargAnswer|child)+(1|item),famil
y=binomial,data=data_TVJT))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: Accuracy ~ group * Constr + group * age_centered + age_centered *
## Constr + TargAnswer + (1 + TargAnswer | child) + (1 | item)
## Data: data_TVJT
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 4387.2  4462.8 -2181.6  4363.2   4020
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -4.3343 -0.6818  0.3205  0.6105  3.0733
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept) 0.6545   0.8090
##      TargAnswer  2.6470   1.6270  -0.84
## item (Intercept) 0.4175   0.6461
## Number of obs: 4032, groups:  child, 125; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.272080   0.230435   1.181 0.237712
## groupDLD          -0.419778   0.136195  -3.082 0.002055 **
## ConstrRelClPhr    -0.277344   0.254448  -1.090 0.275721
## age_centered       0.031853   0.009333   3.413 0.000642 ***
## TargAnswer         1.791062   0.284464   6.296 3.05e-10 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.224760   0.153925  -1.460 0.144236
## groupDLD:age_centered  0.008968   0.012051   0.744 0.456785
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.022441   0.008257  -2.718 0.006572 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##      (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt TrgAns gDLD:C gDLD:_
## groupDLD      -0.297
## CnstrRlClPhr -0.553  0.180
## age_centered  0.006 -0.020 -0.013
## TargAnswer    -0.565 -0.013 -0.005  0.012
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.178 -0.574 -0.312  0.021 -0.004
## grpDLD:g_cn -0.004  0.011  0.006 -0.615  0.002 -0.020
## CnstrRlCP:_ -0.007  0.012  0.008 -0.454 -0.008 -0.016 -0.001
```

```
summary(TVJT_group_constr_TargAnswer_int <- glmer(Accuracy~group*Constr*age_centered+TargAnswer+(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_TVJT))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: Accuracy ~ group * Constr * age_centered + TargAnswer + (1 |
## child) + (1 | item)
## Data: data_TVJT
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 4602.0  4671.3 -2290.0  4580.0    4021
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -3.3684 -0.7896  0.3895  0.6565  2.4332
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 0.1752  0.4186
## item (Intercept) 0.3263  0.5712
## Number of obs: 4032, groups: child, 125; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.265503  0.199883  1.328  0.18408
## groupDLD          -0.386247  0.128743 -3.000  0.00270 **
## ConstrRelClPhr    -0.255072  0.228883 -1.114  0.26510
## age_centered      0.028037  0.009691  2.893  0.00382 **
## TargAnswer        1.549223  0.216017  7.172  7.4e-13 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.198156  0.146692 -1.351  0.17675
## groupDLD:age_centered 0.013856  0.013974  0.992  0.32141
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.017201  0.011020 -1.561  0.11855
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.010279  0.015848 -0.649  0.51658
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##      (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt TrgAns grDLD:CRCP gDLD:_ CRCP:_
## groupDLD -0.329
## CnstrRlClPh -0.573  0.195
## age_centerd 0.011 -0.022 -0.014
## TargAnswer -0.518 -0.012 -0.005  0.011
## grpDLD:CRCP 0.198 -0.578 -0.337  0.019 -0.005
## grpDLD:g_cn -0.010  0.035  0.007 -0.691  0.005 -0.032
## CnstrRlCP:_ -0.011  0.020  0.011 -0.581 -0.006 -0.014  0.401
## gDLD:CRCP:_ 0.008 -0.031 -0.004  0.402 -0.003  0.027 -0.581 -0.694
```

```
anova(TVJT_group_constr_age_TargAnswer, TVJT_Constr_age_int_group_TargAnswer, TVJT_group_constr_int_group_age_int_Constr_age_int_TargAnswer)
```

```
## Data: data_TVJT
## Models:
## TVJT_group_constr_age_TargAnswer: Accuracy ~ group + Constr + age_centered + TargAnswer +
(1 + TargAnswer | child) + (1 | item)
## TVJT_Constr_age_int_group_TargAnswer: Accuracy ~ age_centered * Constr + group + TargAnswer
+ (1 + TargAnswer | child) + (1 | item)
## TVJT_group_constr_int_group_age_int_Constr_age_int_TargAnswer: Accuracy ~ group * Constr +
group * age_centered + age_centered * Constr + TargAnswer + (1 + TargAnswer | child) + (1 | i
tem)
##
## npar AIC
## TVJT_group_constr_age_TargAnswer 9 4391.2
## TVJT_Constr_age_int_group_TargAnswer 10 4385.8
## TVJT_group_constr_int_group_age_int_Constr_age_int_TargAnswer 12 4387.2
##
## BIC logLik
## TVJT_group_constr_age_TargAnswer 4447.9 -2186.6
## TVJT_Constr_age_int_group_TargAnswer 4448.8 -2182.9
## TVJT_group_constr_int_group_age_int_Constr_age_int_TargAnswer 4462.8 -2181.6
##
## deviance Chisq
## TVJT_group_constr_age_TargAnswer 4373.2
## TVJT_Constr_age_int_group_TargAnswer 4365.8 7.4280
## TVJT_group_constr_int_group_age_int_Constr_age_int_TargAnswer 4363.2 2.5798
##
## Df Pr(>Chisq)
## TVJT_group_constr_age_TargAnswer
## TVJT_Constr_age_int_group_TargAnswer 1 0.006422 **
## TVJT_group_constr_int_group_age_int_Constr_age_int_TargAnswer 2 0.275299
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
print(Anova_TVJT_Constr_age_int_group_TargAnswer <- Anova(TVJT_Constr_age_int_group_TargAnswer, type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: Accuracy
##
## Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## age_centered 16.6468 1 4.503e-05 ***
## Constr 2.6379 1 0.104340
## group 22.9105 1 1.697e-06 ***
## TargAnswer 39.7761 1 2.848e-10 ***
## age_centered:Constr 7.5701 1 0.005935 **
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Elicitovaná produkce

```
summary(EP_group_age_Constr <- clmm(score_total ~ group+Constr+age_centered + (1+Constr|child)
+(1+group|item), data=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: score_total ~ group + Constr + age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) +
##          (1 + group | item)
## data:    data_EP_all
##
## link threshold nobs logLik  AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 3812 -3191.01 6406.03 2005(9315) 1.22e-03 1.8e+03
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    2.1754   1.4749
##          ConstrRelClPhr 0.7268   0.8525  -0.721
## item (Intercept)     0.5559   0.7456
##          groupDLD      0.1793   0.4235  -0.528
## Number of groups:  child 126,  item 32
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD      -1.30478    0.23585  -5.532 3.16e-08 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -1.62335    0.26703  -6.079 1.21e-09 ***
## age_centered   0.03216    0.01161   2.770 0.00561 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -1.9250    0.2552  -7.544
## 1|2  -1.3726    0.2539  -5.405
## 2|3  -1.1805    0.2535  -4.657
```

```
summary(EP_group_Constr_int_age <- cllmm(score_total ~ group*Constr+age_centered + (1+Constr|ch
ild)+(1+group|item),data=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: score_total ~ group * Constr + age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) +
##          (1 + group | item)
## data:    data_EP_all
##
## link threshold nobs logLik AIC niter max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 3812 -3188.99 6403.99 1807(8815) 2.65e-03 2.8e+03
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept) 2.2114 1.4871
## ConstrRelClPhr 0.7156 0.8459 -0.741
## item (Intercept) 0.5510 0.7423
## groupDLD 0.1556 0.3945 -0.543
## Number of groups: child 126, item 32
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD -1.71369 0.31075 -5.515 3.49e-08 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -1.96679 0.30980 -6.349 2.17e-10 ***
## age_centered 0.03161 0.01153 2.742 0.00611 **
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 0.53605 0.26550 2.019 0.04349 *
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
## Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1 -2.1768 0.2848 -7.642
## 1|2 -1.6247 0.2837 -5.728
## 2|3 -1.4328 0.2832 -5.058
```

```
summary(EP_group_age_Constr_separ_int <-clmm(score_total ~ group*Constr+group*age_centered+Co
nstr*age_centered + (1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),data=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: score_total ~ group * Constr + group * age_centered + Constr *
##   age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
## data:   data_EP_all
##
## link threshold nobs logLik   AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 3812 -3188.48 6406.96 2164(10207) 5.90e-03 7.3e+03
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    2.2229   1.4909
##   ConstrRelClPhr    0.7089   0.8420  -0.746
## item (Intercept)     0.5507   0.7421
##   groupDLD          0.1555   0.3944  -0.543
## Number of groups:  child 126,  item 32
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD          -1.721055   0.311528  -5.525 3.30e-08 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    -1.974516   0.309695  -6.376 1.82e-10 ***
## age_centered       0.045334   0.019357   2.342  0.0192 *
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr  0.547552   0.265332   2.064  0.0391 *
## groupDLD:age_centered -0.006241   0.022997  -0.271  0.7861
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.011815   0.011976  -0.986  0.3239
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -2.1847   0.2853  -7.657
## 1|2  -1.6326   0.2841  -5.746
## 2|3  -1.4408   0.2837  -5.078
```

```
summary(EP_group_age_Constr_int <- cllmm(score_total ~ group*Constr*age_centered + (1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),data=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: score_total ~ group * Constr * age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) +
##          (1 + group | item)
## data:    data_EP_all
##
## link threshold nobs logLik  AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 3812 -3189.44 6410.89 3418(14634) 2.75e+00 8.1e+03
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    2.0136  1.4190
##          ConstrRelC1Phr 0.6305  0.7940  -0.708
## item (Intercept)     0.5673  0.7532
##          groupDLD      0.1590  0.3988  -0.564
## Number of groups:  child 126,  item 32
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD          -1.3867648  0.2992496  -4.634 3.58e-06 ***
## ConstrRelC1Phr    -1.5754334  0.3147511  -5.005 5.58e-07 ***
## age_centered       0.0345789  0.0212983   1.624  0.104
## groupDLD:ConstrRelC1Phr 0.2910552  0.2590076   1.124  0.261
## groupDLD:age_centered 0.0135040  0.0304655   0.443  0.658
## ConstrRelC1Phr:age_centered -0.0004408  0.0161643  -0.027  0.978
## groupDLD:ConstrRelC1Phr:age_centered -0.0211674  0.0231477  -0.914  0.360
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -1.7475    0.2821  -6.196
## 1|2  -1.1976    0.2814  -4.255
## 2|3  -1.0069    0.2813  -3.580
```

```
anova(EP_group_age_Constr,EP_group_Constr_int_age,EP_group_age_Constr_separ_int,EP_group_age_Constr_int)
```

```
## Likelihood ratio tests of cumulative link models:
##
##                               formula:
## EP_group_age_Constr           score_total ~ group + Constr + age_centered + (1 + Constr |
child) + (1 + group | item)
## EP_group_Constr_int_age       score_total ~ group * Constr + age_centered + (1 + Constr |
child) + (1 + group | item)
## EP_group_age_Constr_separ_int score_total ~ group * Constr + group * age_centered + Constr
* age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
## EP_group_age_Constr_int       score_total ~ group * Constr * age_centered + (1 + Constr |
child) + (1 + group | item)
##                               link: threshold:
## EP_group_age_Constr           logit flexible
## EP_group_Constr_int_age       logit flexible
## EP_group_age_Constr_separ_int logit flexible
## EP_group_age_Constr_int       logit flexible
##
##                               no.par   AIC  logLik LR.stat df Pr(>Chisq)
## EP_group_age_Constr           12 6406.0 -3191.0
## EP_group_Constr_int_age       13 6404.0 -3189.0  4.0420  1  0.04438 *
## EP_group_age_Constr_separ_int 15 6407.0 -3188.5  1.0304  2  0.59739
## EP_group_age_Constr_int       16 6410.9 -3189.4 -1.9314  1  1.00000
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
print(Anova_EP_group_Constr_int_age <- Anova.clm(EP_group_Constr_int_age,type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II tests)
##
## Response: score_total
##           LR Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group           28.4461  1 9.634e-08 ***
## Constr           25.2703  1 4.983e-07 ***
## age_centered     7.3692  1 0.006635 **
## group:Constr     4.0420  1 0.044381 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Měřítka pracovní paměti

Dopředné opakování čísel

```
summary(forwardDS_group <- lm(forward_DS_centered ~ group, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = forward_DS_centered ~ group, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -3.8571 -1.3492 -0.3492  1.1429  4.6508
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)   0.2460     0.2379   1.034   0.303
## groupDLD     -0.4921     0.3364  -1.463   0.146
##
## Residual standard error: 1.888 on 124 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.01696,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.009034
## F-statistic: 2.14 on 1 and 124 DF,  p-value: 0.1461
```

```
summary(forwardDS_group_age <- lm(forward_DS_centered ~ group + age_centered, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = forward_DS_centered ~ group + age_centered, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -4.3201 -1.3031 -0.2134  1.0789  4.9662
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)   0.2460     0.2342   1.050   0.2955
## groupDLD     -0.4921     0.3312  -1.486   0.1399
## age_centered  0.0399     0.0180   2.217   0.0285 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.859 on 123 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.05473,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.03936
## F-statistic: 3.561 on 2 and 123 DF,  p-value: 0.03138
```

```
summary(forwardDS_group_age_int <- lm(forward_DS_centered ~ group *age_centered, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = forward_DS_centered ~ group * age_centered, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -4.2195 -1.2487 -0.1571  1.0884  5.0277
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)      0.24603    0.23496   1.047  0.2971
## groupDLD         -0.49206    0.33229  -1.481  0.1412
## age_centered      0.04767    0.02487   1.917  0.0576 .
## groupDLD:age_centered -0.01644    0.03617  -0.455  0.6502
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.865 on 122 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.05633,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.03313
## F-statistic: 2.428 on 3 and 122 DF,  p-value: 0.06871
```

```
anova(forwardDS_group,forwardDS_group_age,forwardDS_group_age_int)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##
## Model 1: forward_DS_centered ~ group
## Model 2: forward_DS_centered ~ group + age_centered
## Model 3: forward_DS_centered ~ group * age_centered
##   Res.Df    RSS Df Sum of Sq    F Pr(>F)
## 1     124 442.03
## 2     123 425.05  1   16.9838 4.8831 0.02899 *
## 3     122 424.33  1    0.7189 0.2067 0.65018
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
graph_forwardDS <- ggplot(data_sum, aes(x=group, y=forward_DS, fill=group)) + geom_violin(trim=FALSE, color="black", alpha=0.5) + geom_dotplot(binaxis='y', stackdir='center', dotsize=0.35, aes(fill=group), binwidth=1, color=NA) + stat_summary(fun=median, geom="point", size=5, aes(fill=group), shape=21) + scale_fill_brewer(palette="Pastel1") + scale_x_discrete(labels=c("DLD" = "děti s VD", "TD" = "děti s TJV")) + labs(x = "skupina", y = "dopředné opakování čísel") + theme_minimal() + theme(legend.position="none", axis.text=element_text(size=11), axis.title=element_text(size=12))
print(graph_forwardDS)
```


Zpětné opakování čísel

```
summary(backwardDS_group <- lm(backward_DS_centered ~ group, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = backward_DS_centered ~ group, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.2698 -1.3968 -0.2698  0.7302  4.7302
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  -0.4365     0.2072  -2.106  0.03719 *
## groupDLD      0.8730     0.2931   2.979  0.00348 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.645 on 124 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.06678,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.05926
## F-statistic: 8.873 on 1 and 124 DF,  p-value: 0.003482
```

```
summary(backwardDS_group_age <- lm(backward_DS_centered ~ group + age_centered, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = backward_DS_centered ~ group + age_centered, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -3.2945 -0.9594 -0.0819  0.8509  4.4587
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  -0.43651    0.18837  -2.317  0.02214 *
## groupDLD      0.87302    0.26639   3.277  0.00136 **
## age_centered  0.07533    0.01448   5.204  7.92e-07 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.495 on 123 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.2352, Adjusted R-squared:  0.2227
## F-statistic: 18.91 on 2 and 123 DF,  p-value: 6.906e-08
```

```
summary(backwardDS_group_age_int <- lm(backward_DS_centered ~ group* age_centered, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = backward_DS_centered ~ group * age_centered, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -3.4785 -0.9831 -0.1366  0.8499  4.4100
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  -0.43651    0.18854  -2.315  0.02227 *
## groupDLD      0.87302    0.26663   3.274  0.00138 **
## age_centered  0.06320    0.01996   3.167  0.00195 **
## groupDLD:age_centered 0.02565    0.02902   0.884  0.37843
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.496 on 122 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.24, Adjusted R-squared:  0.2214
## F-statistic: 12.84 on 3 and 122 DF,  p-value: 2.382e-07
```

```
anova(backwardDS_group,backwardDS_group_age,backwardDS_group_age_int)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##
## Model 1: backward_DS_centered ~ group
## Model 2: backward_DS_centered ~ group + age_centered
## Model 3: backward_DS_centered ~ group * age_centered
##   Res.Df  RSS Df Sum of Sq      F    Pr(>F)
## 1     124 335.49
## 2     123 274.96  1    60.536 27.0323 8.162e-07 ***
## 3     122 273.21  1     1.750  0.7815  0.3784
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
graph_backward_DS <- ggplot(data_sum, aes(x=group, y=backward_DS, fill=group)) + geom_violin(
  trim=FALSE, color="black", alpha=0.5) + geom_dotplot(binaxis='y', stackdir='center', dotsize
  =0.2, aes(fill=group), binwidth=1, color=NA) + stat_summary(fun=median, geom="point", size=5,
  aes(fill=group), shape=21) + scale_fill_brewer(palette="Pastel1") + scale_x_discrete(labels=c
  ("DLD" = "děti s VD", "TD" = "děti s TJV")) + labs(x = "skupina", y = "zpětné opakování čísel")
  + theme_minimal() + theme(legend.position="none", axis.text=element_text(size=11), axis.t
  itle=element_text(size=12))
print(graph_backward_DS)
```


Opakování pseudoslov

```
summary(NR_group <- lm(NR_centered ~ group, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = NR_centered ~ group, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -8.9839 -1.1746  0.0161  2.0161  6.0161
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)   1.0866     0.3781   2.874 0.00478 **
## groupDLD     -2.1907     0.5369  -4.080 8.03e-05 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 3.001 on 123 degrees of freedom
## (1 observation deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.1192, Adjusted R-squared:  0.112
## F-statistic: 16.65 on 1 and 123 DF,  p-value: 8.034e-05
```

```
summary(NR_group_age <- lm(NR_centered ~ group + age_centered, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = NR_centered ~ group + age_centered, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -9.0987 -1.7578  0.3064  2.3064  5.9655
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)   1.08660     0.37220   2.919 0.00418 **
## groupDLD     -2.17873     0.52852  -4.122 6.87e-05 ***
## age_centered  0.06412     0.02879   2.227 0.02776 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 2.954 on 122 degrees of freedom
## (1 observation deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.1536, Adjusted R-squared:  0.1397
## F-statistic: 11.07 on 2 and 122 DF,  p-value: 3.814e-05
```

```
summary(NR_group_age_int <- lm(NR_centered ~ group*age_centered, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = NR_centered ~ group * age_centered, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -9.118 -1.853  0.310  2.280  5.957
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)      1.08660    0.37354   2.909 0.00432 **
## groupDLD         -2.17665    0.53045  -4.103 7.42e-05 ***
## age_centered      0.05442    0.03954   1.377 0.17120
## groupDLD:age_centered 0.02080    0.05791   0.359 0.72013
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 2.965 on 121 degrees of freedom
## (1 observation deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.1545, Adjusted R-squared:  0.1336
## F-statistic: 7.372 on 3 and 121 DF,  p-value: 0.0001407
```

```
anova(NR_group, NR_group_age, NR_group_age_int)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##
## Model 1: NR_centered ~ group
## Model 2: NR_centered ~ group + age_centered
## Model 3: NR_centered ~ group * age_centered
##   Res.Df    RSS Df Sum of Sq    F Pr(>F)
## 1      123 1108.1
## 2      122 1064.8  1    43.295 4.9253 0.02833 *
## 3      121 1063.6  1     1.134 0.1290 0.72013
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
graph_NR <- ggplot(data_sum, aes(x=group, y=NR, fill=group)) + geom_violin(trim=FALSE, color
="black", alpha=0.5) + geom_dotplot(binaxis='y', stackdir='center', dotsize=0.6, aes(fill=gro
up), binwidth=1, color=NA) + stat_summary(fun=median, geom="point", size=5, aes(fill=group),
shape=21) + scale_fill_brewer(palette="Pastel1") + scale_x_discrete(labels=c("DLD" = "děti s
VD", "TD" = "děti s TJV")) + labs(x = "skupina", y = "opakování pseudoslov") + theme_minimal
() + theme(legend.position="none", axis.text=element_text(size=11), axis.title=element_text(s
ize=12))
print(graph_NR)
```

```
## Warning: Removed 1 row containing non-finite outside the scale range
## (`stat_ydensity()`).
```

```
## Warning: Removed 1 row containing missing values or values outside the scale range
## (`stat_bindot()`).
```

```
## Warning: Removed 1 row containing non-finite outside the scale range  
## (`stat_summary()`).
```


Poslechový test kapacity pracovní paměti s výsledky počítanými po jednotlivých sekvencích

```
summary(LS_seq_group <- lm(LS_seq_centered ~ group, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = LS_seq_centered ~ group, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.3387 -1.3387 -0.3387  1.1587  3.1587
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  -0.2467     0.1790  -1.378  0.1706
## groupDLD      0.4974     0.2542   1.957  0.0526 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.421 on 123 degrees of freedom
## (1 observation deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.0302, Adjusted R-squared:  0.02232
## F-statistic:  3.83 on 1 and 123 DF,  p-value: 0.0526
```

```
summary(LS_seq_group_age <- lm(LS_seq_centered ~ group + age_centered, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = LS_seq_centered ~ group + age_centered, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -3.0878 -0.9885 -0.1320  1.0985  3.0115
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  -0.24673     0.16767  -1.472  0.1437
## groupDLD      0.49886     0.23807   2.095  0.0382 *
## age_centered  0.05497     0.01289   4.265 3.96e-05 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.331 on 122 degrees of freedom
## (1 observation deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.1561, Adjusted R-squared:  0.1422
## F-statistic: 11.28 on 2 and 122 DF,  p-value: 3.199e-05
```

```
summary(LS_seq_group_age_int <- lm(LS_seq_centered ~ group*age_centered, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = LS_seq_centered ~ group * age_centered, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.9717 -0.9082 -0.1575  1.0965  2.9572
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)   -0.24673    0.16809  -1.468  0.144741
## groupDLD       0.49864    0.23867   2.089  0.038783 *
## age_centered  0.06260    0.01779   3.519  0.000612 ***
## groupDLD:age_centered -0.01616    0.02588  -0.624  0.533549
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.334 on 121 degrees of freedom
## (1 observation deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.1588, Adjusted R-squared:  0.1379
## F-statistic: 7.612 on 3 and 121 DF,  p-value: 0.000105
```

```
anova(LS_seq_group,LS_seq_group_age,LS_seq_group_age_int)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##
## Model 1: LS_seq_centered ~ group
## Model 2: LS_seq_centered ~ group + age_centered
## Model 3: LS_seq_centered ~ group * age_centered
##   Res.Df    RSS Df Sum of Sq      F    Pr(>F)
## 1     123 248.30
## 2     122 216.08  1    32.224 18.1032 4.15e-05 ***
## 3     121 215.38  1     0.694  0.3899  0.5335
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
graph_LS_seq <- ggplot(data_sum, aes(x=group, y=LS_seq, fill=group)) + geom_violin(trim=FALSE, color="black", alpha=0.5) + geom_dotplot(binaxis='y', stackdir='center', dotsize=0.2, aes(fill=group), binwidth=1, color=NA) + stat_summary(fun=median, geom="point", size=5, aes(fill=group), shape=21) + scale_fill_brewer(palette="Pastel1") + scale_x_discrete(labels=c("DLD" = "dětí s VD", "TD" = "dětí s TJV")) + labs(x = "skupina", y = "poslechový test kapacity PP (sekvence)") + theme_minimal() + theme(legend.position="none", axis.text=element_text(size=11), axis.title=element_text(size=12))
print(graph_LS_seq)
```

```
## Warning: Removed 1 row containing non-finite outside the scale range
## (`stat_ydensity()`).
```

```
## Warning: Removed 1 row containing missing values or values outside the scale range
## (`stat_bindot()`).
```

```
## Warning: Removed 1 row containing non-finite outside the scale range
## (`stat_summary()`).
```


Poslechový test kapacity pracovní paměti s výsledky počítanými po jednotlivých položkách

```
summary(LS_item_group <- lm(LS_item_centered ~ group, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = LS_item_centered ~ group, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -9.4444 -2.3871  0.5556  1.6129 10.6129
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  0.02844    0.48970   0.058   0.954
## groupDLD    -0.05735    0.69533  -0.082   0.934
##
## Residual standard error: 3.887 on 123 degrees of freedom
## (1 observation deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  5.53e-05, Adjusted R-squared:  -0.008074
## F-statistic: 0.006802 on 1 and 123 DF, p-value: 0.9344
```

```
summary(LS_item_group_age <- lm(LS_item_centered ~ group + age_centered, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = LS_item_centered ~ group + age_centered, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -8.3048 -2.0535  0.2758  2.2457  8.8359
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)   0.02844    0.46292   0.061 0.951105
## groupDLD     -0.05371    0.65731  -0.082 0.935010
## age_centered  0.14071    0.03558   3.955 0.000129 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 3.674 on 122 degrees of freedom
## (1 observation deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.1137, Adjusted R-squared:  0.09916
## F-statistic: 7.824 on 2 and 122 DF,  p-value: 0.0006351
```

```
summary(LS_item_group_age_int <- lm(LS_item_centered ~ group*age_centered, data_sum))
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = LS_item_centered ~ group * age_centered, data = data_sum)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -8.4686 -2.1065  0.3738  2.2658  8.6842
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)   0.02844    0.46464   0.061 0.95129
## groupDLD     -0.05340    0.65974  -0.081 0.93562
## age_centered  0.12993    0.04918   2.642 0.00933 **
## groupDLD:age_centered 0.02279    0.07153   0.319 0.75056
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 3.688 on 121 degrees of freedom
## (1 observation deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.1144, Adjusted R-squared:  0.09247
## F-statistic: 5.212 on 3 and 121 DF,  p-value: 0.00203
```

```
anova(LS_item_group,LS_item_group_age,LS_item_group_age_int)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##
## Model 1: LS_item_centered ~ group
## Model 2: LS_item_centered ~ group + age_centered
## Model 3: LS_item_centered ~ group * age_centered
##   Res.Df    RSS Df Sum of Sq      F    Pr(>F)
## 1     123 1858.3
## 2     122 1647.1  1   211.168 15.5259 0.0001366 ***
## 3     121 1645.7  1     1.381  0.1015 0.7505627
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
graph_LS_item <- ggplot(data_sum, aes(x=group, y=LS_item, fill=group)) + geom_violin(trim=FALSE, color="black", alpha=0.5) + geom_dotplot(binaxis='y', stackdir='center', dotsize=0.7, aes(fill=group), binwidth=1, color=NA) + stat_summary(fun=median, geom="point", size=5, aes(fill=group), shape=21) + scale_fill_brewer(palette="Pastel1") + scale_x_discrete(labels=c("DLD" = "děti s VD", "TD" = "děti s TJV")) + labs(x = "skupina", y = "poslechový test kapacity PP (po ložky)") + theme_minimal() + theme(legend.position="none", axis.text=element_text(size=11), axis.title=element_text(size=12))
print(graph_LS_item)
```

```
## Warning: Removed 1 row containing non-finite outside the scale range
## (`stat_ydensity()`).
```

```
## Warning: Removed 1 row containing missing values or values outside the scale range
## (`stat_bindot()`).
```

```
## Warning: Removed 1 row containing non-finite outside the scale range
## (`stat_summary()`).
```


Korelace mezi paměťovými testy

Děti s VD

```
variables_VD <- data_sum_VD[, c("NR_centered", "forward_DS_centered", "backward_DS_centered",
"LS_seq_centered", "LS_item_centered")]
cor_table_VD <- cor(variables_VD, use="complete.obs", method="pearson")
colnames(cor_table_VD) <- c("opakování pseudoslov", "dopředné opakování čísel", "zpětné opako
vání čísel", "poslechový test PP (sekvence)", "poslechový test PP (položky)")
rownames(cor_table_VD) <- c("opakování pseudoslov", "dopředné opakování čísel", "zpětné opako
vání čísel", "poslechový test PP (sekvence)", "poslechový test PP (položky)")
corrplot(cor_table_VD, method="circle", type="upper", diag=FALSE,addCoef.col = "black",numbe
r.cex = 0.7, cl.lim=c(-1,1), tl.col = "black", tl.cex = 0.8,col=colorRampPalette(c("blue", "w
hite", "red"))(200))
```

```
## Warning in text.default(pos.xlabel[, 1], pos.xlabel[, 2], newcolnames, srt =
## tl.srt, : "cl.lim" is not a graphical parameter
```

```
## Warning in text.default(pos.ylabel[, 1], pos.ylabel[, 2], newrownames, col =
## tl.col, : "cl.lim" is not a graphical parameter
```

```
## Warning in title(title, ...): "cl.lim" is not a graphical parameter
```


Děti s TJV

```
variables_TJV <- data_sum_TJV[, c("NR_centered", "forward_DS_centered", "backward_DS_centered", "LS_seq_centered", "LS_item_centered")]
cor_table_TJV <- cor(variables_TJV, use="complete.obs", method="pearson")
colnames(cor_table_TJV) <- c("opakování pseudoslov", "dopředné opakování čísel", "zpětné opakování čísel", "poslechový test PP (sekvence)", "poslechový test PP (položky)")
rownames(cor_table_TJV) <- c("opakování pseudoslov", "dopředné opakování čísel", "zpětné opakování čísel", "poslechový test PP (sekvence)", "poslechový test PP (položky)")
corrplot(cor_table_TJV, method="circle", type="upper", diag=FALSE, addCoef.col = "black", number.cex = 0.7, cl.lim=c(-1,1), tl.col = "black", tl.cex = 0.8, col=colorRampPalette(c("blue", "white", "red"))(200))
```

```
## Warning in text.default(pos.xlabel[, 1], pos.xlabel[, 2], newcolnames, srt =
## tl.srt, : "cl.lim" is not a graphical parameter
```

```
## Warning in text.default(pos.ylabel[, 1], pos.ylabel[, 2], newrownames, col =
## tl.col, : "cl.lim" is not a graphical parameter
```

```
## Warning in title(title, ...): "cl.lim" is not a graphical parameter
```


Souvislost opakování vět s pracovní pamětí a jazykovou schopností

Role krátkodobé fonologické paměti (opakování pseudoslov)

```
summary(errors_group_constr_NR_int <- clmm(num_changes ~ group*Constr*NR + (1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item), data=data_SI))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: num_changes ~ group * Constr * NR + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 +
##   group | item)
## data:   data_SI
##
## link threshold nobs logLik  AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible  5893 -7672.21 15380.43 5371(37729) 1.47e-02 2.4e+03
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    2.1642  1.4711
##   ConstrRelClPhr  0.1016  0.3188  0.418
## item (Intercept)    1.1542  1.0743
##   groupDLD        0.1061  0.3257 -0.451
## Number of groups:  child 125,  item 48
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD          1.29054    0.30668   4.208 2.57e-05 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    1.26640    0.34189   3.704 0.000212 ***
## NR                -0.22842    0.07449  -3.066 0.002167 **
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr  0.02806    0.16427   0.171 0.864362
## groupDLD:NR        0.09239    0.09547   0.968 0.333183
## ConstrRelClPhr:NR   0.03277    0.03270   1.002 0.316188
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr:NR -0.04598    0.04212  -1.092 0.274959
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -2.1968    0.3441  -6.383
## 1|2  -0.8742    0.3425  -2.552
## 2|3   0.2459    0.3422   0.718
## 3|4   1.2836    0.3426   3.747
## 4|5   2.2957    0.3434   6.685
## (153 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
print(Anova_II_errors_group_constr_NR_int <-
Anova.clmm(errors_group_constr_NR_int,type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II tests)
##
## Response: num_changes
##           LR Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group      17.649  1 2.656e-05 ***
## Constr     15.171  1 9.819e-05 ***
## NR         44.196  1 2.970e-11 ***
## group:Constr  0.007  1  0.9333
## group:NR      0.878  1  0.3487
## Constr:NR     0.060  1  0.8063
## group:Constr:NR 1.186  1  0.2762
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
plot(effect("group:Constr:NR",errors_group_constr_NR_int),axes=list(grid=TRUE, y=list(style="stacked",lab="počet změn (pravděpodobnost)")),lines=list(multiline=TRUE),lattice=list(key.args=list(space="right",columns=1,border=TRUE,fontfamily="serif",cex=1.25,cex.title=1.5)))
```

```
## Warning in Analyze.model(focal.predictors, mod, xlevels, default.levels, : the
## predictor NR is a one-column matrix that was converted to a vector
```

group*Constr*NR effect plot

Role centrální exekutivy (poslechový test kapacity)

pracovní paměti)

```
summary(errors_group_constr_LS_item_int <- clmm(num_changes ~ group*Constr*LS_item + (1+Constr
|child)+(1+group|item),data=data_SI))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: num_changes ~ group * Constr * LS_item + (1 + Constr | child) +
##      (1 + group | item)
## data:      data_SI
##
## link threshold nobs logLik  AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible  5893 -7596.02 15228.05 4092(28894) 1.81e-02 2.8e+03
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    1.7174   1.3105
##      ConstrRelClPhr  0.1067   0.3266  0.545
## item (Intercept)     1.1580   1.0761
##      groupDLD        0.1168   0.3418 -0.442
## Number of groups:  child 125,  item 48
##
## Coefficients:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD          1.756935    0.264771    6.636 3.23e-11 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    1.306373    0.340674    3.835 0.000126 ***
## LS_item           -0.279400    0.046762   -5.975 2.30e-09 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr  0.008581    0.163147    0.053 0.958051
## groupDLD:LS_item    0.122836    0.065185    1.884 0.059509 .
## ConstrRelClPhr:LS_item  0.013642    0.023834    0.572 0.567071
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr:LS_item 0.018573    0.033357    0.557 0.577662
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -1.9506    0.3239  -6.023
## 1|2  -0.6282    0.3223  -1.949
## 2|3   0.4865    0.3222   1.510
## 3|4   1.5195    0.3228   4.708
## 4|5   2.5380    0.3238   7.839
## (153 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
print(Anova_II_errors_group_constr_LS_item_int <- Anova.clmm(errors_group_constr_LS_item_int,
type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II tests)
##
## Response: num_changes
##
##          LR Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group          38.553  1  5.330e-10 ***
## Constr          15.469  1  8.388e-05 ***
## LS_item        193.077  1  < 2.2e-16 ***
## group:Constr     0.005  1  0.94484
## group:LS_item    3.508  1  0.06108 .
## Constr:LS_item   1.868  1  0.17175
## group:Constr:LS_item 0.309  1  0.57816
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
plot(effect("group:Constr:LS_item",errors_group_constr_LS_item_int),axes=list(grid=TRUE, y=list(style="stacked",lab="number of changes (probability)")),lines=list(multiline=TRUE),lattice=list(key.args=list(space="right",columns=1,border=TRUE,fontfamily="serif",cex=1.25,cex.title=1.5)))
```

```
## Warning in Analyze.model(focal.predictors, mod, xlevels, default.levels, : the
## predictor LS_item is a one-column matrix that was converted to a vector
```

group*Constr*LS_item effect plot

Role širší jazykové znalosti (test slovní zásoby)

```
summary(errors_group_constr_vocab_int <- cLmm(num_changes ~ group*Constr*vocab + (1+Constr|chi
ld)+(1+group|item),data=data_SI))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: num_changes ~ group * Constr * vocab + (1 + Constr | child) +
##          (1 + group | item)
## data:    data_SI
##
## link threshold nobs logLik  AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 5941 -7672.17 15380.33 3852(23642) 2.47e-02 2.5e+04
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    1.71563  1.3098
##          ConstrRelClPhr 0.08945  0.2991  0.435
## item (Intercept)     1.15793  1.0761
##          groupDLD       0.10501  0.3241  -0.463
## Number of groups:  child 126,  item 48
##
## Coefficients:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD          1.699403    0.262256   6.480 9.18e-11 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    1.296166    0.340308   3.809 0.00014 ***
## vocab              -0.096148    0.015501  -6.203 5.54e-10 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 0.030913    0.157757   0.196 0.84464
## groupDLD:vocab    0.044572    0.021998   2.026 0.04274 *
## ConstrRelClPhr:vocab 0.005045    0.007636   0.661 0.50880
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr:vocab -0.020142    0.011048  -1.823 0.06829 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -1.9679    0.3238  -6.077
## 1|2  -0.6444    0.3223  -1.999
## 2|3   0.4752    0.3222   1.475
## 3|4   1.5119    0.3227   4.685
## 4|5   2.5262    0.3237   7.804
## (105 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
print(Anova_II_errors_group_constr_vocab_int <- Anova.clm(errors_group_constr_vocab_int,type
="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II tests)
##
## Response: num_changes
##                LR Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group          38.151  1  6.546e-10 ***
## Constr         15.249  1  9.421e-05 ***
## vocab           39.016  1  4.203e-10 ***
## group:Constr    0.040  1   0.84072
## group:vocab     3.531  1   0.06023 .
## Constr:vocab    0.644  1   0.42235
## group:Constr:vocab 3.283  1   0.07001 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
plot(effect("group:Constr:vocab",errors_group_constr_vocab_int),axes=list(grid=TRUE, y=list(s
style="stacked",lab="number of changes (probability)")),lines=list(multiline=TRUE),lattice=lis
t(key.args=list(space="right",columns=1,border=TRUE,fontfamily="serif",cex=1.25,cex.title=1.
5)))
```

```
## Warning in Analyze.model(focal.predictors, mod, xlevels, default.levels, : the
## predictor vocab is a one-column matrix that was converted to a vector
```

group*Constr*vocab effect plot

Role znalosti cílových syntaktických struktur

Opakování vztažných vět

```
summary(changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests <-clmm(num_changes ~ group + TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs
+ EP_adj + EP_rightRCs + (1|child)+(1+group|item),data=data_SI_RelClPhr))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: num_changes ~ group + TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs + EP_adj + EP_rightRCs +
## (1 | child) + (1 + group | item)
## data: data_SI_RelClPhr
##
## link threshold nobs logLik AIC niter max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 3954 -4924.66 9877.31 2598(13127) 1.44e-02 3.7e+04
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept) 1.4321 1.197
## item (Intercept) 1.0569 1.028
## groupDLD 0.1005 0.317 -0.508
## Number of groups: child 126, item 32
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD 0.48349 0.26351 1.835 0.06653 .
## TVJT_adj -0.56428 0.56093 -1.006 0.31442
## TVJT_embRCs -1.62600 0.58781 -2.766 0.00567 **
## EP_adj -0.00173 0.01230 -0.141 0.88816
## EP_rightRCs -0.08042 0.01530 -5.258 1.46e-07 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
## Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1 -5.0205 0.5361 -9.365
## 1|2 -3.8070 0.5329 -7.143
## 2|3 -2.7769 0.5311 -5.229
## 3|4 -1.8249 0.5297 -3.445
## 4|5 -0.8671 0.5290 -1.639
## (78 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
summary(changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests_int <-clmm(num_changes ~ group*(TVJT_adj + TVJT_embR
Cs + EP_adj + EP_rightRCs) + (1|child)+(1+group|item),data=data_SI_RelClPhr))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula:
## num_changes ~ group * (TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs + EP_adj + EP_rightRCs) +
##   (1 | child) + (1 + group | item)
## data:   data_SI_RelClPhr
##
## link threshold nobs logLik   AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible  3954 -4923.12 9882.24 3641(18165) 2.29e+00 1.8e+05
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept) 1.39182  1.1798
## item  (Intercept) 1.05431  1.0268
##      groupDLD     0.09539  0.3088  -0.517
## Number of groups:  child 126,  item 32
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD      -0.256434   1.003055  -0.256  0.79822
## TVJT_adj      -0.207847   1.015639  -0.205  0.83785
## TVJT_embRCs   -2.646149   0.878328  -3.013  0.00259 **
## EP_adj         0.005752   0.020034   0.287  0.77401
## EP_rightRCs   -0.081187   0.018257  -4.447 8.71e-06 ***
## groupDLD:TVJT_adj -0.600561   1.221228  -0.492  0.62288
## groupDLD:TVJT_embRCs 1.906360   1.177666   1.619  0.10550
## groupDLD:EP_adj    -0.014703   0.026237  -0.560  0.57521
## groupDLD:EP_rightRCs 0.008209   0.033472   0.245  0.80625
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -5.4240    0.8444  -6.423
## 1|2  -4.2090    0.8423  -4.997
## 2|3  -3.1784    0.8409  -3.780
## 3|4  -2.2254    0.8399  -2.650
## 4|5  -1.2674    0.8394  -1.510
## (78 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
anova(changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests,changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests_int) # interakce význ
amně nepřispívá k vysvětlení variability s ohledem na závislou proměnnou
```

```
## Likelihood ratio tests of cumulative link models:
##
##                               formula:
## changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests  num_changes ~ group + TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs + EP_adj
+ EP_rightRCs + (1 | child) + (1 + group | item)
## changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests_int num_changes ~ group * (TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs + EP_ad
j + EP_rightRCs) + (1 | child) + (1 + group | item)
##                               link: threshold:
## changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests  logit flexible
## changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests_int logit flexible
##
##                               no.par    AIC  logLik LR.stat df
## changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests      14 9877.3 -4924.7
## changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests_int   18 9882.2 -4923.1  3.0718  4
##                               Pr(>Chisq)
## changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests
## changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests_int    0.5459
```

```
print(Anova_II_changes_RelCl_group_allLangTests <- Anova.clmm(changes_RelCl_group_allLangTest
s, type = "II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II tests)
##
## Response: num_changes
##           LR Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group      3.5732  1  0.058720 .
## TVJT_adj    1.0112  1  0.314623
## TVJT_embRCs 7.4121  1  0.006478 **
## EP_adj      0.0198  1  0.888130
## EP_rightRCs 25.0326 1 5.637e-07 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Opakování jednoduchých vět s nominální frází s adjektivem

```
summary(changes_Adj_group_allLangTests <- clmm(num_changes ~ group + TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs +
EP_adj + EP_rightRCs + (1|child)+(1+group|item), data = data_SI_AdjPhr))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: num_changes ~ group + TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs + EP_adj + EP_rightRCs +
## (1 | child) + (1 + group | item)
## data: data_SI_AdjPhr
##
## link threshold nobs logLik AIC niter max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 1987 -2793.27 5614.54 2104(10457) 2.58e-04 4.1e+04
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept) 1.5524 1.2460
## item (Intercept) 1.3626 1.1673
## groupDLD 0.1273 0.3568 -0.353
## Number of groups: child 126, item 16
##
## Coefficients:
## Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD 0.631472 0.287814 2.194 0.028233 *
## TVJT_adj -1.287802 0.593961 -2.168 0.030147 *
## TVJT_embRCs -2.154398 0.625651 -3.443 0.000574 ***
## EP_adj -0.002363 0.013105 -0.180 0.856893
## EP_rightRCs -0.074638 0.016422 -4.545 5.49e-06 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
## Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1 -5.121190 0.616033 -8.313
## 1|2 -3.617382 0.610708 -5.923
## 2|3 -2.353254 0.607706 -3.872
## 3|4 -1.159324 0.605792 -1.914
## 4|5 0.005434 0.605030 0.009
## (27 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
summary(changes_Adj_group_allLangTests_int <- clmm(num_changes ~ group*(TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs + EP_adj + EP_rightRCs) + (1|child)+(1+group|item), data = data_SI_AdjPhr))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula:
## num_changes ~ group * (TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs + EP_adj + EP_rightRCs) +
##   (1 | child) + (1 + group | item)
## data:   data_SI_AdjPhr
##
## link threshold nobs logLik   AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 1987 -2790.61 5617.22 3705(16530) 2.28e+00 1.9e+05
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept) 1.4685   1.2118
## item (Intercept) 1.3720   1.1713
## groupDLD          0.1416   0.3764  -0.328
## Number of groups:  child 126,  item 16
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD          -0.447918   1.065345  -0.420 0.674161
## TVJT_adj           -1.089139   1.075337  -1.013 0.311139
## TVJT_embRCs        -3.185624   0.928329  -3.432 0.000600 ***
## EP_adj             -0.003306   0.021192  -0.156 0.876032
## EP_rightRCs        -0.071713   0.019504  -3.677 0.000236 ***
## groupDLD:TVJT_adj  -0.293595   1.285144  -0.228 0.819294
## groupDLD:TVJT_embRCs 2.140259   1.239782   1.726 0.084290 .
## groupDLD:EP_adj     -0.001358   0.027638  -0.049 0.960817
## groupDLD:EP_rightRCs 0.002141   0.035224   0.061 0.951529
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -5.6585   0.9278  -6.099
## 1|2  -4.1536   0.9238  -4.496
## 2|3  -2.8812   0.9215  -3.127
## 3|4  -1.6840   0.9201  -1.830
## 4|5  -0.5232   0.9199  -0.569
## (27 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
anova(changes_Adj_group_allLangTests,changes_Adj_group_allLangTests_int) # interakce významně nepřispívá k vysvětlení variability s ohledem na závislou proměnnou
```

```
## Likelihood ratio tests of cumulative link models:
##
##                               formula:
## changes_Adj_group_allLangTests  num_changes ~ group + TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs + EP_adj +
EP_rightRCs + (1 | child) + (1 + group | item)
## changes_Adj_group_allLangTests_int num_changes ~ group * (TVJT_adj + TVJT_embRCs + EP_adj
+ EP_rightRCs) + (1 | child) + (1 + group | item)
##                               link: threshold:
## changes_Adj_group_allLangTests  logit flexible
## changes_Adj_group_allLangTests_int logit flexible
##
##                               no.par   AIC  logLik LR.stat df Pr(>Chisq)
## changes_Adj_group_allLangTests      14 5614.5 -2793.3
## changes_Adj_group_allLangTests_int   18 5617.2 -2790.6  5.3234  4    0.2557
```

```
print(anova_II_changes_Adj_group_allLangTests <- Anova.clmm(changes_Adj_group_allLangTests, t
ype = "II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II tests)
##
## Response: num_changes
##           LR Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group      4.7237  1  0.0297493 *
## TVJT_adj    4.6353  1  0.0313216 *
## TVJT_embRCs 11.3648  1  0.0007485 ***
## EP_adj      0.0325  1  0.8569089
## EP_rightRCs 19.3724  1  1.075e-05 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Analýzy pouze s prediktory porozumění a produkce nominálním frázím s adjektivem

```
summary(changes_Adj_group_EP <- clmm(num_changes ~ group + TVJT_adj + EP_adj + (1|child)+(1+g
roup|item), data = data_SI_AdjPhr))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: num_changes ~ group + TVJT_adj + EP_adj + (1 | child) + (1 +
##   group | item)
## data:   data_SI_AdjPhr
##
## link threshold nobs logLik   AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 1987 -2808.24 5640.49 1964(9737) 3.48e-03 2.2e+04
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept) 2.0440    1.4297
## item (Intercept) 1.3559    1.1644
##   groupDLD      0.1254    0.3541  -0.327
## Number of groups: child 126, item 16
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD  0.95387    0.31569   3.022 0.002515 **
## TVJT_adj -2.41926    0.63085  -3.835 0.000126 ***
## EP_adj   -0.05336    0.01096  -4.869 1.12e-06 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##           Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -4.4196    0.5878  -7.519
## 1|2  -2.9232    0.5831  -5.013
## 2|3  -1.6617    0.5807  -2.862
## 3|4  -0.4654    0.5794  -0.803
## 4|5   0.7032    0.5793   1.214
## (27 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
summary(changes_Adj_group_EP_int <- clmm(num_changes ~ group*(TVJT_adj + EP_adj) + (1|child)+
(1+group|item), data = data_SI_AdjPhr))
```

```
## Cumulative Link Mixed Model fitted with the Laplace approximation
##
## formula: num_changes ~ group * (TVJT_adj + EP_adj) + (1 | child) + (1 +
##   group | item)
## data:   data_SI_AdjPhr
##
## link threshold nobs logLik  AIC      niter      max.grad cond.H
## logit flexible 1987 -2806.55 5641.09 2830(13883) 2.25e+00 1.2e+05
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept) 1.9454  1.3948
## item (Intercept) 1.3473  1.1607
##   groupDLD      0.1304  0.3611  -0.303
## Number of groups: child 126, item 16
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## groupDLD          0.60007   1.01713   0.590  0.5552
## TVJT_adj         -2.42891   1.17240  -2.072  0.0383 *
## EP_adj           -0.07347   0.01853  -3.964 7.36e-05 ***
## groupDLD:TVJT_adj 0.47389   1.38354   0.343  0.7320
## groupDLD:EP_adj   0.03451   0.02291   1.506  0.1320
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Threshold coefficients:
##      Estimate Std. Error z value
## 0|1  -4.4972   0.9089  -4.948
## 1|2  -3.0086   0.9057  -3.322
## 2|3  -1.7556   0.9041  -1.942
## 3|4  -0.5671   0.9035  -0.628
## 4|5   0.5948   0.9039   0.658
## (27 observations deleted due to missingness)
```

```
anova(changes_Adj_group_EP,changes_Adj_group_EP_int)
```

```
## Likelihood ratio tests of cumulative link models:
##
##              formula:
## changes_Adj_group_EP  num_changes ~ group + TVJT_adj + EP_adj + (1 | child) + (1 + group | item)
## changes_Adj_group_EP_int num_changes ~ group * (TVJT_adj + EP_adj) + (1 | child) + (1 + group | item)
##
##              link: threshold:
## changes_Adj_group_EP  logit flexible
## changes_Adj_group_EP_int logit flexible
##
##              no.par    AIC  logLik LR.stat df Pr(>Chisq)
## changes_Adj_group_EP      12 5640.5 -2808.2
## changes_Adj_group_EP_int  14 5641.1 -2806.5  3.3961  2    0.183
```

Produkce cílových struktur u dětí s VD a TJV

Snaha o použití vztažných vět a nominálních frází s adjektivem

Opakování vět

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group <- glmer(use_struct_binom~group+Constr +(1+Constr|child)+
(1+group|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group + Constr + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 +
## group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##          AIC          BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
##    5574.1    5634.3  -2778.0   5556.1     5932
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -10.0123  -0.4757   0.1878   0.4770   5.1444
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name             Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child  (Intercept)      3.38269  1.8392
##        ConstrRelClPhr  1.17885  1.0857  0.05
## item   (Intercept)      0.53147  0.7290
##        groupDLD         0.07316  0.2705  -0.85
## Number of obs: 5941, groups:  child, 126; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)    1.0849    0.3085   3.516 0.000438 ***
## groupDLD      -1.2996    0.3626  -3.584 0.000338 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -0.3159    0.2246  -1.407 0.159553
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD
## groupDLD     -0.658
## CnstrRlClPh -0.427  0.080
```

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int <- glmer(use_struct_binom~group*Constr +(1+Constr|chil
d)+(1+group|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 +
## group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 5572.4 5639.3 -2776.2 5552.4 5931
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -10.4052  -0.4778   0.1865   0.4785   5.3779
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name              Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)        3.28050  1.8112
##      ConstrRelClPhr 1.14573  1.0704  0.09
## item (Intercept)         0.51047  0.7145
##      groupDLD         0.05925  0.2434  -0.86
## Number of obs: 5941, groups: child, 126; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.94827   0.30541   3.105 0.001904 **
## groupDLD         -1.16650   0.35235  -3.311 0.000931 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    0.04027   0.28299   0.142 0.886830
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.51506   0.26144  -1.970 0.048829 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP
## groupDLD    -0.658
## CnstrRlClPh -0.437  0.154
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.194 -0.146 -0.629
```

```
anova(SI_use_struct_Constr_group, SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int)
```

```
## Data: data_SI
## Models:
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group: use_struct_binom ~ group + Constr + (1 + Constr | child) + (1
+ group | item)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + (1 + Constr | child) +
(1 + group | item)
##              npar      AIC      BIC logLik deviance Chisq Df
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group          9 5574.1 5634.3 -2778.1 5556.1
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int     10 5572.4 5639.3 -2776.2 5552.4 3.6984 1
##              Pr(>Chisq)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int    0.05446 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
print(Anova_SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int <- Anova(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int,type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: use_struct_binom
##              Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group        13.2260  1  0.0002761 ***
## Constr         1.9958  1  0.1577354
## group:Constr   3.8812  1  0.0488289 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
plot(allEffects(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int), multiline = TRUE, ci.style = "bars", axes=list(y=list(GRID = TRUE, lab="použití cílové struktury")), lattice=list(key.args=list(space="right", columns=1, border=TRUE, fontfamily="serif")))
```

group*Constr effect plot

Zapojení efektu věku

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age <- glmer(use_struct_binom~group+Constr+age_centered + (1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group + Constr + age_centered + (1 + Constr |
## child) + (1 + group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 5555.5  5622.4 -2767.8  5535.5    5931
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -10.4352  -0.4761   0.1867   0.4768   5.1220
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name             Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)      2.71089  1.6465
##      ConstrRelClPhr  1.19678  1.0940  0.13
## item (Intercept)       0.53037  0.7283
##      groupDLD         0.07398  0.2720 -0.85
## Number of obs: 5941, groups: child, 126; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)    1.05867    0.29239   3.621 0.000294 ***
## groupDLD      -1.24271    0.33396  -3.721 0.000198 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -0.32078    0.22490  -1.426 0.153778
## age_centered   0.08259    0.01747   4.729 2.26e-06 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP
## groupDLD     -0.659
## CnstrRlClPh -0.440  0.100
## age_centerd  0.002  0.003 -0.009
```

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age <- glmer(use_struct_binom~group*Constr+age_centered
+(1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + age_centered + (1 + Constr |
## child) + (1 + group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 5553.4  5627.0 -2765.7  5531.4    5930
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -10.8537  -0.4793   0.1867   0.4779   5.3793
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name              Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)        2.62734  1.6209
##      ConstrRelClPhr  1.16128  1.0776  0.17
## item (Intercept)         0.50832  0.7130
##      groupDLD         0.05885  0.2426 -0.87
## Number of obs: 5941, groups: child, 126; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.93325    0.28747   3.246 0.001169 **
## groupDLD         -1.13831    0.32116  -3.544 0.000394 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    0.05454    0.28297   0.193 0.847148
## age_centered      0.08240    0.01726   4.773 1.82e-06 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.54369    0.26220  -2.074 0.038122 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt
## groupDLD      -0.653
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.437  0.146
## age_centerd   0.005 -0.004 -0.005
## grpDLD:CRCP   0.176 -0.109 -0.630  0.000
```

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int <- glmer(use_struct_binom
~group*Constr+Constr*age_centered+group*age_centered +(1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),family=
binomial,data=data_SI))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + Constr * age_centered + group *
## age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 5554.7  5641.7 -2764.3  5528.7    5928
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -10.7445  -0.4773   0.1848   0.4764   5.3930
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name             Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)      2.63078  1.6220
##      ConstrRelClPhr  1.13496  1.0653  0.15
## item (Intercept)       0.51771  0.7195
##      groupDLD         0.06218  0.2494 -0.87
## Number of obs: 5941, groups: child, 126; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.93924    0.28897   3.250 0.001153 **
## groupDLD         -1.14430    0.32196  -3.554 0.000379 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    0.04810    0.28404   0.169 0.865513
## age_centered      0.10779    0.02418   4.457 8.3e-06 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.53296    0.26137  -2.039 0.041436 *
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.01252    0.01389  -0.901 0.367428
## groupDLD:age_centered -0.04948    0.03456  -1.432 0.152238
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt gDLD:C CRCP:_
## groupDLD      -0.656
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.452  0.160
## age_centerd   0.014 -0.014 -0.015
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.195 -0.132 -0.634  0.021
## CnstrRlCP:_  -0.014  0.012  0.013 -0.105 -0.017
## grpDLD:g_cn -0.009  0.010  0.009 -0.695 -0.016  0.032
```

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age_int <- glmer(use_struct_binom~group*Constr*age_centered
+(1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr * age_centered + (1 + Constr |
## child) + (1 + group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 5556.6  5650.2 -2764.3  5528.6    5927
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -10.8480  -0.4778   0.1854   0.4759   5.4221
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name              Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)        2.62291  1.6195
##      ConstrRelClPhr  1.13469  1.0652  0.15
## item (Intercept)         0.51609  0.7184
##      groupDLD          0.06139  0.2478  -0.87
## Number of obs: 5941, groups: child, 126; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.937775   0.288573   3.250 0.001155 **
## groupDLD         -1.142344   0.321534  -3.553 0.000381 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    0.049324   0.283774   0.174 0.862012
## age_centered      0.106858   0.024192   4.417 1e-05 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.535552   0.261267  -2.050 0.040381 *
## groupDLD:age_centered -0.047999   0.034645  -1.385 0.165914
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.007321   0.019455  -0.376 0.706692
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.010450   0.027586  -0.379 0.704810
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt grDLD:CRCP gDLD:_ CRCP:_
## groupDLD      -0.655
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.450  0.158
## age_centerd   0.013 -0.014 -0.014
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.192 -0.129 -0.634  0.019
## grpDLD:g_cn  -0.008  0.010  0.008 -0.696 -0.014
## CnstrRlCP:_  -0.017  0.018  0.015 -0.134 -0.027  0.090
## gDLD:CRCP:_  0.010 -0.013 -0.009  0.092  0.023  -0.102 -0.701
```

```
anova(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age,SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age, SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int,SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age_int)
```

```
## Data: data_SI
## Models:
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age: use_struct_binom ~ group + Constr + age_centered + (1 + Co
nstr | child) + (1 + group | item)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + age_centered + (1
+ Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int: use_struct_binom ~ group * Co
nstr + Constr * age_centered + group * age_centered + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 + group | ite
m)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age_int: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr * age_centered + (1
+ Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
##
## npar    AIC    BIC
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age                10 5555.5 5622.4
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age            11 5553.4 5627.0
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int 13 5554.7 5641.7
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age_int           14 5556.6 5650.2
##
## logLik deviance
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age                -2767.8  5535.5
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age            -2765.7  5531.4
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int -2764.3  5528.7
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age_int           -2764.3  5528.6
##
## Chisq Df
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age                4.1047  1
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age            2.7438  2
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int 0.1380  1
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_age_int           0.71033
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
print(Anova_SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age <- Anova(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age,ty
pe="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: use_struct_binom
##          Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group      14.3863  1 0.0001489 ***
## Constr       2.0531  1 0.1519000
## age_centered 22.7807  1 1.816e-06 ***
## group:Constr  4.2996  1 0.0381224 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Elicitovaná produkce

Model paralelní k modelu s opakováním vět jako závislou proměnnou.

```
summary(EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int <- glmer(use_struct_binom~group*Constr +(1+Constr|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 |
## item)
## Data: data_EP_all
##
## AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 3501.8   3551.7 -1742.9  3485.8    3804
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.9007 -0.4101  0.2296  0.4561  4.0879
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    3.4944   1.8693
##      ConstrRelClPhr  2.7606   1.6615  -0.57
## item (Intercept)     0.5829   0.7635
## Number of obs: 3812, groups:  child, 126; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.5735     0.3345   7.693 1.43e-14 ***
## groupDLD          -1.0069     0.3732  -2.698 0.006974 **
## ConstrRelClPhr   -1.3851     0.3809  -3.636 0.000277 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.3761     0.3633  -1.035 0.300605
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP
## groupDLD     -0.586
## CnstrRlClPh -0.662  0.321
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.375 -0.624 -0.506
```

```
print(Anova_EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int <- Anova(EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int,type="I
I"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: use_struct_binom
##              Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group         18.3258  1  1.862e-05 ***
## Constr        23.2772  1  1.402e-06 ***
## group:Constr   1.0715  1    0.3006
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
plot(allEffects(EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int), multiline = TRUE, ci.style = "bars", axes=list(y=list(GRID = TRUE, lab="použití cílové struktury")), lattice=list(key.args=list(space="right", columns=1, border=TRUE, fontfamily="serif")))
```

group*Constr effect plot

Zapojení efektu věku

```
summary(EP_use_struct_Constr_group_age <- glmer(use_struct_binom~Constr+group+age_centered + (1|child)+(1|item), family=binomial, data=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ Constr + group + age_centered + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_EP_all
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 3621.9  3659.3 -1804.9  3609.9    3806
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -7.6788 -0.4900  0.2641  0.5062  4.4429
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 1.8720    1.3682
## item (Intercept)  0.4745    0.6889
## Number of obs: 3812, groups: child, 126; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)    2.45091    0.26291   9.322 < 2e-16 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -1.42131    0.26067  -5.453 4.96e-08 ***
## groupDLD       -1.15469    0.26189  -4.409 1.04e-05 ***
## age_centered   0.04982    0.01419   3.511 0.000447 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) CnsRCP grpDLD
## CnstrRlClPhr -0.521
## groupDLD     -0.520  0.014
## age_centerd  0.025 -0.013 -0.013
```

```
summary(EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age <- glmer(use_struct_binom~Constr*group+age_centered +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ Constr * group + age_centered + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_EP_all
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 3618.6 3662.3 -1802.3 3604.6 3805
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -7.0597 -0.4844  0.2658  0.5054  4.7646
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 1.8850  1.3730
## item (Intercept) 0.4721  0.6871
## Number of obs: 3812, groups: child, 126; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.30074    0.26923   8.546 < 2e-16 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -1.18795    0.27743  -4.282 1.85e-05 ***
## groupDLD         -0.89446    0.28440  -3.145 0.001661 **
## age_centered      0.05017    0.01424   3.524 0.000425 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr:groupDLD -0.42341    0.18088  -2.341 0.019243 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) CnsRCP grpDLD ag_cnt
## CnstrRlClPh -0.551
## groupDLD    -0.553  0.143
## age_centerd  0.022 -0.008 -0.007
## CnstRCP:DLD  0.223 -0.348 -0.384 -0.013
```

```
summary(EP_use_struct_group_Constr_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int <- glmer(use_struct_binom
~group*Constr+Constr*age_centered + group*age_centered+(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,dat
a=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + Constr * age_centered + group *
## age_centered + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## Data: data_EP_all
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 3620.7  3676.9 -1801.3  3602.7    3803
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.7121 -0.4822  0.2670  0.5025  4.9833
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 1.8522  1.3610
## item (Intercept) 0.4714  0.6866
## Number of obs: 3812, groups: child, 126; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.287483   0.268197   8.529 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD         -0.882185   0.282489  -3.123  0.00179 **
## ConstrRelClPhr   -1.178804   0.277468  -4.248 2.15e-05 ***
## age_centered      0.029539   0.020408   1.447  0.14779
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.432977   0.180988  -2.392  0.01674 *
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered 0.004581   0.009736   0.471  0.63796
## groupDLD:age_centered 0.037236   0.028242   1.318  0.18735
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##          (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt gDLD:C CRCP:_
## groupDLD -0.552
## CnstrRlClPh -0.553  0.143
## age_centerd 0.032 -0.020 -0.019
## grpDLD:CRCP 0.225 -0.386 -0.349  0.018
## CnstrRlCP:_ -0.035  0.003  0.045 -0.294 -0.040
## grpDLD:g_cn -0.012  0.023  0.003 -0.664 -0.025  0.016
```

```
summary(EP_use_struct_group_Constr_age_int <- glmer(use_struct_binom~Constr*group*age_centered+(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_EP_all))
```

```

## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ Constr * group * age_centered + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_EP_all
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 3622.2 3684.7 -1801.1 3602.2 3802
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.5145 -0.4831  0.2667  0.5036  4.8037
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 1.8502  1.3602
## item (Intercept) 0.4719  0.6869
## Number of obs: 3812, groups: child, 126; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.28195    0.26815  8.510 < 2e-16 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -1.17127    0.27766 -4.218 2.46e-05 ***
## groupDLD         -0.87012    0.28286 -3.076 0.0021 **
## age_centered      0.02556    0.02116  1.208 0.2271
## ConstrRelClPhr:groupDLD -0.44502    0.18167 -2.450 0.0143 *
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered 0.01102    0.01341  0.822 0.4113
## groupDLD:age_centered 0.04528    0.03051  1.484 0.1377
## ConstrRelClPhr:groupDLD:age_centered -0.01351    0.01948 -0.694 0.4879
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) CnsRCP grpDLD ag_cnt CnRCP:DLD CRCP:_ gDLD:_
## CnstrRlClPh -0.553
## groupDLD    -0.551  0.144
## age_centerd  0.034 -0.025 -0.031
## CnstRCP:DLD  0.225 -0.350 -0.389  0.034
## CnstrRlCP:_ -0.039  0.054  0.036 -0.388 -0.081
## grpDLD:g_cn -0.019  0.014  0.043 -0.693 -0.056  0.269
## CnRCP:DLD:_  0.025 -0.034 -0.057  0.267  0.090  -0.688 -0.379

```

```

anova(EP_use_struct_Constr_group_age,EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age,EP_use_struct_group_C
onstr_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int,EP_use_struct_group_Constr_age_int)

```

```
## Data: data_EP_all
## Models:
## EP_use_struct_Constr_group_age: use_struct_binom ~ Constr + group + age_centered + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age: use_struct_binom ~ Constr * group + age_centered + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## EP_use_struct_group_Constr_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + Constr * age_centered + group * age_centered + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## EP_use_struct_group_Constr_age_int: use_struct_binom ~ Constr * group * age_centered + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
##
##                               npar   AIC   BIC
## EP_use_struct_Constr_group_age           6 3621.9 3659.3
## EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age        7 3618.6 3662.3
## EP_use_struct_group_Constr_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int  9 3620.7 3676.9
## EP_use_struct_group_Constr_age_int       10 3622.2 3684.7
##
##                               logLik deviance
## EP_use_struct_Constr_group_age        -1804.9   3609.9
## EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age     -1802.3   3604.6
## EP_use_struct_group_Constr_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int -1801.3   3602.7
## EP_use_struct_group_Constr_age_int     -1801.1   3602.2
##
##                               Chisq Df
## EP_use_struct_Constr_group_age
## EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age      5.2651  1
## EP_use_struct_group_Constr_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int 1.9046  2
## EP_use_struct_group_Constr_age_int      0.4656  1
##
##                               Pr(>Chisq)
## EP_use_struct_Constr_group_age
## EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age      0.02176 *
## EP_use_struct_group_Constr_int_Constr_age_int_group_age_int 0.38586
## EP_use_struct_group_Constr_age_int      0.49504
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
print(Anova_EP_use_struct_Constr_group_age <- Anova(EP_use_struct_Constr_group_int_age,type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: use_struct_binom
##           Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## Constr    29.5627  1 5.414e-08 ***
## group     19.1725  1 1.194e-05 ***
## age_centered 12.4189  1 0.000425 ***
## Constr:group  5.4793  1 0.019243 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Gramatická správnost použití vztažného zájmena a adjektiva v jádru struktury

Opakování vět

```
summary(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~Constr+group +(1+Constr|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI_core))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ Constr + group + (1 + Constr | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_SI_core
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2900.9  2943.5 -1443.5  2886.9    3217
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -4.2596  0.1502  0.3201  0.4889  1.9029
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    1.4811   1.2170
## ConstrRelClPhr     1.5840   1.2586  -0.81
## item (Intercept)     0.6201   0.7875
## Number of obs: 3224, groups:  child, 122; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)    2.7236     0.2756   9.884 < 2e-16 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -1.1898     0.3056  -3.893 9.88e-05 ***
## groupDLD       -0.5980     0.1793  -3.335 0.000853 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) CnsRCP
## CnstrRlClPh -0.793
## groupDLD    -0.295 -0.003
```

```
summary(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~group*Constr +(1+Constr|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI_core))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + (1 + Constr | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_SI_core
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2896.5  2945.2 -1440.3  2880.5    3216
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -4.8618  0.1468  0.3233  0.4903  1.8286
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name             Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)      1.402    1.1840
##      ConstrRelClPhr  1.475    1.2145  -0.80
## item (Intercept)       0.623    0.7893
## Number of obs: 3224, groups: child, 122; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)          3.0873    0.3301  9.353 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD              -1.2743    0.3225 -3.951 7.78e-05 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr       -1.6416    0.3680 -4.461 8.16e-06 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr  0.8792    0.3514  2.502  0.0124 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP
## groupDLD      -0.571
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.856  0.473
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.487 -0.838 -0.526
```

```
anova(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group,SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int)
```

```
## Data: data_SI_core
## Models:
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group: gram_in_core_binom ~ Constr + group + (1 + Constr | child) +
## (1 | item)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + (1 + Constr | chil
## d) + (1 | item)
##              npar      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance  Chisq Df
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group          7 2900.9 2943.5 -1443.5  2886.9
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int      8 2896.5 2945.2 -1440.3  2880.5 6.3797  1
##              Pr(>Chisq)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int  0.01154 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
print(Anova_SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int <- Anova(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int,type
="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: gram_in_core_binom
##              Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group        11.5593  1  0.0006741 ***
## Constr       13.6753  1  0.0002173 ***
## group:Constr  6.2583  1  0.0123615 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
plot(allEffects(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int), multiline = TRUE, ci.style = "bars",axes=1
list(y=list(GRID = TRUE, lab="použití wh-slova v jádru vztažné věty")),lattice=list(key.args=1
list(space="right",columns=1,border=TRUE,fontfamily="serif")))
```

group*Constr effect plot

Zapojení efektu věku

Model s více než jednou interakcí s náhodným sklonem nekonverguje => používané modely bez náhodných sklonů.

```
summary(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~Constr+group+age_centere
d +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI_core))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ Constr + group + age_centered + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_SI_core
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2925.1  2961.6 -1456.5  2913.1    3218
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -5.8358  0.1799  0.3499  0.4962  2.0935
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 0.4812  0.6937
## item (Intercept) 0.5778  0.7602
## Number of obs: 3224, groups: child, 122; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)  2.486020   0.243076  10.227 < 2e-16 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -1.019940   0.262378  -3.887 0.000101 ***
## groupDLD      -0.603708   0.167204  -3.611 0.000305 ***
## age_centered  0.015249   0.009196   1.658 0.097278 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) CnsRCP grpDLD
## CnstrRlClPhr -0.752
## groupDLD     -0.346  0.029
## age_centerd -0.033 -0.004  0.021
```

```
summary(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int <- glmer(gram_in_core_b
inom~group*Constr+age_centered*Constr+age_centered*group +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,
data=data_SI_core))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + age_centered * Constr +
## age_centered * group + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## Data: data_SI_core
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2914.8  2969.5 -1448.4  2896.8    3215
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.0374  0.1646  0.3440  0.5053  2.0963
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 0.4259  0.6526
## item (Intercept) 0.5733  0.7572
## Number of obs: 3224, groups: child, 122; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.75077    0.26466  10.394 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD         -1.09947    0.23476  -4.683 2.82e-06 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -1.36900    0.29259  -4.679 2.88e-06 ***
## age_centered      0.05335    0.01590   3.356 0.00079 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 0.71020    0.23008   3.087 0.00202 **
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.02614    0.01238  -2.111 0.03476 *
## groupDLD:age_centered -0.03885    0.01781  -2.182 0.02914 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt gDLD:C CRCP:_
## groupDLD      -0.513
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.802  0.351
## age_centerd   0.008 -0.038 -0.032
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.396 -0.723 -0.440  0.093
## CnstrRlCP:_  -0.025  0.077  0.011 -0.636 -0.097
## grpDLD:g_cn  0.006 -0.024  0.022 -0.601 -0.045  0.110
```

```
summary(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~group*Constr*age_centered +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI_core))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr * age_centered + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_SI_core
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2915.4  2976.1 -1447.7  2895.4    3214
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.4444  0.1694  0.3411  0.5029  2.1602
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 0.4250  0.6519
## item (Intercept) 0.5739  0.7576
## Number of obs: 3224, groups: child, 122; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.74575    0.26416  10.394 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD         -1.10369    0.23369  -4.723 2.32e-06 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -1.36800    0.29214  -4.683 2.83e-06 ***
## age_centered      0.03805    0.01999   1.904 0.05696 .
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr
##              0.72622    0.22936   3.166 0.00154 **
## groupDLD:age_centered
##              -0.01557    0.02594  -0.600 0.54826
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered
##              -0.00745    0.01946  -0.383 0.70176
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered
##              -0.03074    0.02515  -1.222 0.22156
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt grDLD:CRCP gDLD:_ CRCP:_
## groupDLD      -0.510
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.801  0.348
## age_centerd  -0.023  0.026  0.009
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.391 -0.720 -0.436 -0.011
## grpDLD:g_cn  0.020 -0.052 -0.008 -0.770  0.036
## CnstrRlCP:_  0.011 -0.010 -0.025 -0.790  0.030    0.609
## gDLD:CRCP:_ -0.008  0.037  0.019  0.611 -0.080   -0.728 -0.773
```

```
anova(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age,SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int,SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int)
```

```
## Data: data_SI_core
## Models:
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age: gram_in_core_binom ~ Constr + group + age_centered + (1
| child) + (1 | item)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int: gram_in_core_binom ~ group
* Constr + age_centered * Constr + age_centered * group + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr * age_centered +
(1 | child) + (1 | item)
##
##                               npar    AIC
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age                6 2925.1
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int    9 2914.8
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int                10 2915.4
##
##                               BIC  logLik
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age                2961.6 -1456.5
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int 2969.5 -1448.4
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int                2976.2 -1447.7
##
##                               deviance  Chisq
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age                2913.1
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int    2896.8 16.2917
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int                2895.4  1.4271
##
##                               Df Pr(>Chisq)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int    3  0.0009881 ***
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int                1  0.2322437
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
print(Anova_SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int <- Anova(SI_gram_in
_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int,type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: gram_in_core_binom
##
##              Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group          13.9030  1  0.0001925 ***
## Constr          14.1648  1  0.0001675 ***
## age_centered     3.0117  1  0.0826641 .
## group:Constr     9.5282  1  0.0020234 **
## Constr:age_centered 4.4567  1  0.0347646 *
## group:age_centered 4.7593  1  0.0291401 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Elicitovaná produkce

Model s dvojcestnou interakcí s náhodným sklonem nekonverguje => použití modelu pouze s náhodným interceptem.

```
summary(EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~group*Constr +(1|child)+
(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_EP_all)) #
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## Data: data_EP_all
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2376.4  2411.8 -1182.2  2364.4    2665
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -7.1305 -0.3919  0.2209  0.4642  4.6059
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 1.587    1.260
## item (Intercept) 1.178    1.085
## Number of obs: 2671, groups: child, 126; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      3.2172   0.3550   9.061 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD          -2.1468   0.2947  -7.284 3.24e-13 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -2.3954   0.4296  -5.575 2.47e-08 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 0.9779   0.2452   3.987 6.68e-05 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP
## groupDLD      -0.487
## CnstrRlClPh -0.654  0.198
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.278 -0.477 -0.334
```

```
print(Anova_EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int <- Anova(EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int,type
="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: gram_in_core_binom
##              Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group        37.493  1  9.174e-10 ***
## Constr       20.268  1  6.732e-06 ***
## group:Constr 15.900  1  6.678e-05 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
plot(allEffects(EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int), multiline = TRUE, ci.style = "bars", axes=list(y=list(GRID = TRUE, lab="použití adjektiva v cílové struktuře")), lattice=list(key.args=list(space="right", columns=1, border=TRUE, fontfamily="serif")))
```

group*Constr effect plot**Zapojení efektu věku**

```
summary(EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~Constr+group+age_centered +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ Constr + group + age_centered + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_EP_all
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2388.8  2424.1 -1188.4  2376.8    2665
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.7052 -0.3889  0.2342  0.4590  5.3474
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 1.564      1.250
## item (Intercept) 1.245      1.116
## Number of obs: 2671, groups: child, 126; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)    2.85945    0.34420   8.307 < 2e-16 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -1.85121    0.41462  -4.465 8.01e-06 ***
## groupDLD       -1.61856    0.25648  -6.311 2.78e-10 ***
## age_centered    0.02469    0.01383   1.785  0.0743 .
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) CnsRCP grpDLD
## CnstrRlClPh -0.621
## groupDLD    -0.402  0.036
## age_centerd  0.017 -0.010 -0.041
```

```
summary(EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~group*Constr+age_centered +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + age_centered + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_EP_all
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2375.0  2416.3 -1180.5  2361.0    2664
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.8908 -0.3942  0.2190  0.4654  4.5196
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 1.525     1.235
## item (Intercept) 1.178     1.085
## Number of obs: 2671, groups: child, 126; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      3.22224    0.35380   9.108 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD         -2.16624    0.29154  -7.430 1.08e-13 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -2.40169    0.42975  -5.589 2.29e-08 ***
## age_centered      0.02567    0.01372   1.871  0.0613 .
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 0.98720    0.24527   4.025 5.70e-05 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt
## groupDLD      -0.486
## CnstrRlClPh -0.657  0.201
## age_centerd  0.024 -0.048 -0.018
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.280 -0.484 -0.334  0.022
```

```
summary(EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int <- glmer(gram_in_core_b
inom~group*Constr+age_centered*Constr+age_centered*group +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,
data=data_EP_all))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + age_centered * Constr +
## age_centered * group + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## Data: data_EP_all
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2377.0  2430.0 -1179.5  2359.0    2662
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.6656 -0.3907  0.2181  0.4672  4.6284
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 1.501      1.225
## item (Intercept) 1.179      1.086
## Number of obs: 2671, groups: child, 126; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      3.235085   0.354065   9.137 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD         -2.174018   0.291726  -7.452 9.18e-14 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -2.412921   0.430411  -5.606 2.07e-08 ***
## age_centered      0.046532   0.021053   2.210  0.0271 *
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 1.008830   0.249023   4.051 5.10e-05 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.003122   0.013294  -0.235  0.8143
## groupDLD:age_centered -0.039482   0.027511  -1.435  0.1513
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt gDLD:C CRCP:_
## groupDLD      -0.488
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.659  0.205
## age_centerd   0.057 -0.081 -0.041
## grpDLD:CRCP   0.286 -0.493 -0.337  0.111
## CnstrRlCP:_   -0.047  0.090  0.035 -0.434 -0.164
## grpDLD:g_cn  -0.035  0.023  0.024 -0.670 -0.053  0.113
```

```
summary(EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~group*Constr*age_centered +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_EP_all))
```

```

## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr * age_centered + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_EP_all
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2377.2  2436.1 -1178.6  2357.2    2661
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.3700 -0.4014  0.2174  0.4705  4.4016
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 1.518    1.232
## item (Intercept) 1.179    1.086
## Number of obs: 2671, groups: child, 126; item, 32
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      3.27508    0.35719   9.169 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD         -2.20185    0.29549  -7.451 9.23e-14 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -2.44911    0.43248  -5.663 1.49e-08 ***
## age_centered      0.06171    0.02394   2.578 0.00994 **
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 1.01251    0.25224   4.014 5.97e-05 ***
## groupDLD:age_centered -0.06176    0.03209  -1.925 0.05427 .
## ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered -0.02452    0.02056  -1.193 0.23297
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr:age_centered 0.03698    0.02713   1.363 0.17283
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP ag_cnt grDLD:CRCP gDLD:_ CRCP:_
## groupDLD      -0.496
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.662  0.215
## age_centerd   0.111 -0.132 -0.084
## grpDLD:CRCP   0.294 -0.500 -0.343  0.137
## grpDLD:g_cn  -0.086  0.071  0.064 -0.747 -0.069
## CnstrRlCP:_  -0.118  0.141  0.090 -0.604 -0.150    0.452
## gDLD:CRCP:_   0.094 -0.081 -0.071  0.460  0.020   -0.506 -0.758

```

```

anova(EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age,EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age, EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int,EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int)

```

```
## Data: data_EP_all
## Models:
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age: gram_in_core_binom ~ Constr + group + age_centered + (1
| child) + (1 | item)
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + age_centered +
(1 | child) + (1 | item)
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int: gram_in_core_binom ~ group
* Constr + age_centered * Constr + age_centered * group + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr * age_centered +
(1 | child) + (1 | item)
##
## npar AIC
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age 6 2388.8
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age 7 2375.0
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int 9 2377.0
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int 10 2377.2
##
## BIC logLik
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age 2424.1 -1188.4
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age 2416.2 -1180.5
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int 2430.0 -1179.5
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int 2436.1 -1178.6
##
## deviance Chisq
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age 2376.8
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age 2361.0 15.7567
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int 2359.0 2.0437
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int 2357.2 1.7872
##
## Df Pr(>Chisq)
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age 1 7.203e-05 ***
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age_Constr_int_age_group_int 2 0.3599
## EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_age_int 1 0.1813
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
print(Anova_EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age <- Anova(EP_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_age, type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: gram_in_core_binom
## Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group 39.2516 1 3.726e-10 ***
## Constr 20.2638 1 6.747e-06 ***
## age_centered 3.5008 1 0.06134 .
## group:Constr 16.2009 1 5.697e-05 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Role centrální exekutivy při opakování cílových

struktur

Snaha o zopakování cílové struktury

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_LS <- glmer(use_struct_binom~group+Constr+LS_item +(1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group + Constr + LS_item + (1 + Constr | child) +
## (1 + group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 5506.4  5573.2 -2743.2  5486.4    5883
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -11.1508  -0.4760   0.1810   0.4778   5.2077
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)    2.62212  1.6193
## ConstrRelClPhr      1.13974  1.0676  0.04
## item (Intercept)     0.53109  0.7288
## groupDLD             0.07455  0.2730 -0.85
## Number of obs: 5893, groups: child, 125; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)    1.09179    0.28745   3.798 0.000146 ***
## groupDLD      -1.33079    0.32633  -4.078 4.54e-05 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -0.33618    0.22445  -1.498 0.134174
## LS_item        0.23745    0.04133   5.746 9.15e-09 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP
## groupDLD     -0.646
## CnstrRlClPh -0.463  0.088
## LS_item       0.012 -0.023 -0.002
```

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS <- glmer(use_struct_binom~group*Constr+LS_item +(1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + LS_item + (1 + Constr | child) +
## (1 + group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 5504.3 5577.7 -2741.1 5482.3 5882
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -11.5424  -0.4780   0.1809   0.4807   5.3883
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name             Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)      2.54271  1.5946
##      ConstrRelClPhr  1.09805  1.0479  0.08
## item (Intercept)       0.50849  0.7131
##      groupDLD         0.05885  0.2426 -0.87
## Number of obs: 5893, groups: child, 125; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.94280   0.28547   3.303 0.000958 ***
## groupDLD         -1.18177   0.31867  -3.709 0.000208 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   0.03934   0.28123   0.140 0.888757
## LS_item          0.23504   0.04100   5.733 9.86e-09 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.54221   0.25881  -2.095 0.036171 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP LS_itm
## groupDLD      -0.650
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.479  0.180
## LS_item       0.010 -0.019 -0.013
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.218 -0.181 -0.627  0.022
```

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int <- glmer(use_struct_binom~group*Constr+group*LS_item +(1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI))
```

```
## Warning in checkConv(attr(opt, "derivs"), opt$par, ctrl = control$checkConv, :
## Model failed to converge with max|grad| = 0.00219369 (tol = 0.002, component 1)
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + group * LS_item + (1 + Constr |
## child) + (1 + group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##  5505.5   5585.6  -2740.7   5481.5     5881
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -11.9060  -0.4782   0.1792   0.4802   5.3622
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name             Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)      2.53811  1.5931
##      ConstrRelClPhr  1.09782  1.0478  0.07
## item (Intercept)       0.51212  0.7156
##      groupDLD         0.06055  0.2461 -0.87
## Number of obs: 5893, groups: child, 125; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.94496    0.28592   3.305 0.000950 ***
## groupDLD         -1.18103    0.31868  -3.706 0.000211 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   0.03612    0.28198   0.128 0.898075
## LS_item          0.27412    0.05977   4.586 4.52e-06 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.53926    0.25920  -2.080 0.037481 *
## groupDLD:LS_item -0.07343    0.08186  -0.897 0.369707
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP LS_itm gDLD:C
## groupDLD     -0.652
## CnstrRlClPh -0.483  0.185
## LS_item       0.014 -0.014 -0.018
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.225 -0.188 -0.630  0.023
## grpDLD:LS_t -0.009  0.003  0.012 -0.729 -0.013
## optimizer (Nelder_Mead) convergence code: 0 (OK)
## Model failed to converge with max|grad| = 0.00219369 (tol = 0.002, component 1)
```

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int <- glmer(use_struct_binom~g
roup*Constr+group*LS_item+Constr*LS_item +(1+Constr|child)+(1+group|item),family=binomial,dat
a=data_SI))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + group * LS_item + Constr *
## LS_item + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 5507.4  5594.3 -2740.7  5481.4    5880
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -11.9653  -0.4788   0.1794   0.4806   5.3729
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name             Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)      2.53330  1.5916
##      ConstrRelClPhr  1.09974  1.0487  0.07
## item (Intercept)       0.51139  0.7151
##      groupDLD         0.06041  0.2458 -0.87
## Number of obs: 5893, groups: child, 125; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.94417   0.28576   3.304 0.000953 ***
## groupDLD         -1.18008   0.31857  -3.704 0.000212 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    0.03751   0.28200   0.133 0.894177
## LS_item          0.27297   0.06049   4.512 6.41e-06 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.54138   0.25997  -2.082 0.037300 *
## groupDLD:LS_item  -0.07289   0.08191  -0.890 0.373524
## ConstrRelClPhr:LS_item  0.00354   0.03420   0.103 0.917570
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP LS_itm gDLD:C gDLD:L
## groupDLD      -0.652
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.482  0.185
## LS_item        0.017 -0.019 -0.021
## grpDLD:CRCP   0.224 -0.188 -0.630  0.034
## grpDLD:LS_t  -0.010  0.004  0.013 -0.726 -0.016
## CnstRCP:LS_  -0.021  0.031  0.028 -0.161 -0.073  0.049
```

```
summary(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_LS_int <- glmer(use_struct_binom~group*Constr*LS_item +(1+
Constr|child)+(1+group|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI)) # nekonverguje
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr * LS_item + (1 + Constr | child) +
## (1 + group | item)
## Data: data_SI
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 5509.1 5602.7 -2740.6 5481.1 5879
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -12.3839  -0.4786   0.1788   0.4804   5.3389
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name             Variance Std.Dev. Corr
## child (Intercept)      2.52291  1.5884
##      ConstrRelClPhr  1.09057  1.0443  0.08
## item (Intercept)       0.50945  0.7138
##      groupDLD         0.05924  0.2434 -0.87
## Number of obs: 5893, groups: child, 125; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      0.94085    0.28512   3.300 0.000967 ***
## groupDLD         -1.17827    0.31781  -3.707 0.000209 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   0.04158    0.28139   0.148 0.882516
## LS_item          0.26712    0.06077   4.396 1.1e-05 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr -0.54121    0.25904  -2.089 0.036684 *
## groupDLD:LS_item -0.06408    0.08273  -0.775 0.438625
## ConstrRelClPhr:LS_item  0.02599    0.05070   0.513 0.608153
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr:LS_item -0.03997    0.06733  -0.594 0.552758
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP LS_itm grDLD:CRCP gDLD:L CRCP:L
## groupDLD      -0.651
## CnstrRlClPhr -0.480  0.181
## LS_item        0.017 -0.017 -0.021
## grpDLD:CRCP   0.220 -0.183 -0.629  0.027
## grpDLD:LS_t  -0.010  0.002  0.013 -0.730 -0.007
## CnstRCP:LS_  -0.026  0.026  0.033 -0.210 -0.047    0.149
## gDLD:CRCP:L   0.016 -0.007 -0.021  0.152 -0.002   -0.171 -0.740
```

```
anova(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_LS,SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS,SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int,SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int)
```

```
## Data: data_SI
## Models:
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_LS: use_struct_binom ~ group + Constr + LS_item + (1 + Constr |
child) + (1 + group | item)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + LS_item + (1 + Constr |
child) + (1 + group | item)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + group * L
S_item + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + group * LS_item + Constr * LS_item + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
##
##                               npar   AIC   BIC
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_LS           10 5506.4 5573.2
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS        11 5504.3 5577.7
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int 12 5505.5 5585.6
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int 13 5507.4 5594.3
##
##                               loglik deviance
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_LS          -2743.2   5486.4
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS      -2741.1   5482.3
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int -2740.7   5481.5
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int -2740.7   5481.4
##
##                               Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_LS
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS        4.1795  1    0.04092
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int 0.7953  1    0.37249
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int 0.0101  1    0.91994
##
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_LS
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS        *
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
anova(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS,SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int)
```

```
## Data: data_SI
## Models:
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + LS_item + (1 + Constr |
child) + (1 + group | item)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int: use_struct_binom ~ group * Constr + group * LS_item + Constr * LS_item + (1 + Constr | child) + (1 + group | item)
##
##                               npar   AIC   BIC
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS        11 5504.3 5577.7
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int 13 5507.4 5594.3
##
##                               loglik deviance
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS      -2741.1   5482.3
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int -2740.7   5481.4
##
##                               Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS
## SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int 0.8055  2    0.6685
```

```
print(Anova_SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS <- Anova(SI_use_struct_Constr_group_int_LS,type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: use_struct_binom
##           Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group      17.2656  1  3.250e-05 ***
## Constr       2.2746  1   0.13151
## LS_item     32.8679  1  9.864e-09 ***
## group:Constr  4.3890  1   0.03617 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Gramatická správnost použití cílového lexému v jádru struktury

```
summary(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_LS <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~group+Constr+LS_item +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI_core))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group + Constr + LS_item + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_SI_core
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2886.3  2922.7 -1437.1  2874.3    3178
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.5756  0.1781  0.3473  0.4994  1.8433
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 0.4236  0.6509
## item (Intercept) 0.5772  0.7598
## Number of obs: 3184, groups: child, 121; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)    2.47490    0.24103  10.268 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD       -0.64690    0.16167  -4.001 6.29e-05 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr -1.02170    0.26245  -3.893 9.91e-05 ***
## LS_item         0.06865    0.02234   3.073 0.00212 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP
## groupDLD     -0.335
## CnstrRlClPh -0.758  0.032
## LS_item      -0.022 -0.038 -0.010
```

```
summary(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~group*Constr+LS_item
+(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI_core))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + LS_item + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_SI_core
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2879.8  2922.3 -1432.9  2865.8    3177
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -7.7836  0.1662  0.3436  0.5076  1.6904
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 0.4096  0.6400
## item (Intercept) 0.5773  0.7598
## Number of obs: 3184, groups: child, 121; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.75791    0.26396  10.448 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD         -1.13966    0.23296  -4.892 9.98e-07 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -1.37777    0.29249  -4.711 2.47e-06 ***
## LS_item           0.06914    0.02212   3.126 0.00177 **
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 0.67147    0.22890   2.934 0.00335 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP LS_itm
## groupDLD     -0.505
## CnstrRlClPh -0.803  0.348
## LS_item      -0.015 -0.034 -0.014
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.391 -0.724 -0.435  0.011
```

```
summary(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS_group_int <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~group*Const
r+LS_item*group +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI_core))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + LS_item * group + (1 |
## child) + (1 | item)
## Data: data_SI_core
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2879.4  2927.9 -1431.7  2863.4    3176
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -8.0731  0.1643  0.3411  0.5073  1.7847
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 0.3937  0.6275
## item (Intercept) 0.5746  0.7580
## Number of obs: 3184, groups: child, 121; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.74636    0.26320  10.434 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD         -1.11128    0.23259  -4.778 1.77e-06 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr   -1.38057    0.29215  -4.726 2.29e-06 ***
## LS_item           0.10467    0.03126   3.348 0.000814 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 0.67842    0.22887   2.964 0.003034 **
## groupDLD:LS_item -0.06982    0.04381  -1.594 0.110967
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP LS_itm gDLD:C
## groupDLD      -0.505
## CnstrRlClPhr -0.804  0.349
## LS_item       -0.021  0.027 -0.019
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.393 -0.725 -0.437  0.021
## grpDLD:LS_t  0.019 -0.080  0.012 -0.714 -0.016
```

```
summary(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~group*Constr+group*LS_item+Constr*LS_item +(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI_core))
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + group * LS_item + Constr *
## LS_item + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## Data: data_SI_core
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2880.0  2934.6 -1431.0  2862.0    3175
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -8.6621  0.1588  0.3403  0.5098  1.9394
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 0.3968  0.6299
## item (Intercept) 0.5745  0.7579
## Number of obs: 3184, groups: child, 121; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.75560    0.26401  10.437 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD         -1.13717    0.23450  -4.849 1.24e-06 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr  -1.38756    0.29281  -4.739 2.15e-06 ***
## LS_item           0.13535    0.04062   3.332 0.000861 ***
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 0.71339    0.23178   3.078 0.002085 **
## groupDLD:LS_item  -0.07557    0.04418  -1.711 0.087163 .
## ConstrRelClPhr:LS_item -0.03799    0.03209  -1.184 0.236464
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP LS_itm gDLD:C gDLD:L
## groupDLD      -0.509
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.805  0.353
## LS_item        0.019 -0.052 -0.042
## grpDLD:CRCP   0.397 -0.729 -0.439  0.112
## grpDLD:LS_t   0.006 -0.054  0.023 -0.617 -0.047
## CnstRCP:LS_  -0.040  0.098  0.028 -0.636 -0.132  0.109
```

```
summary(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_LS_int <- glmer(gram_in_core_binom~group*Constr*LS_item
+(1|child)+(1|item),family=binomial,data=data_SI_core)) # nekonverguje
```

```
## Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Laplace
## Approximation) [glmerMod]
## Family: binomial ( logit )
## Formula: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr * LS_item + (1 | child) +
## (1 | item)
## Data: data_SI_core
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2881.4  2942.0 -1430.7  2861.4    3174
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -8.2641  0.1617  0.3414  0.5084  2.0319
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## child (Intercept) 0.3992  0.6319
## item (Intercept) 0.5761  0.7590
## Number of obs: 3184, groups:  child, 121; item, 48
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept)      2.750920   0.263849  10.426 < 2e-16 ***
## groupDLD          -1.139790   0.233895  -4.873 1.10e-06 ***
## ConstrRelClPhr    -1.385051   0.292625  -4.733 2.21e-06 ***
## LS_item           0.110698   0.050729   2.182 0.02910 *
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr 0.724646   0.231412   3.131 0.00174 **
## groupDLD:LS_item  -0.037007   0.065453  -0.565 0.57180
## ConstrRelClPhr:LS_item -0.007369   0.049782  -0.148 0.88233
## groupDLD:ConstrRelClPhr:LS_item -0.051743   0.065168  -0.794 0.42721
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##          (Intr) grpDLD CnsRCP LS_itm grDLD:CRCP gDLD:L CRCP:L
## groupDLD  -0.506
## CnstrRlClPh  -0.804  0.349
## LS_item      0.003 -0.002 -0.017
## grpDLD:CRCP  0.391 -0.725 -0.434  0.020
## grpDLD:LS_t  0.006 -0.065  0.006 -0.774  0.033
## CnstRCP:LS_ -0.018  0.021  0.004 -0.786 -0.006    0.608
## gDLD:CRCP:L  0.006  0.031  0.004  0.599 -0.080   -0.737 -0.764
```

```
anova(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_LS,SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS,SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS_group_int,SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int)
```

```

## Data: data_SI_core
## Models:
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_LS: gram_in_core_binom ~ group + Constr + LS_item + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + LS_item + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS_group_int: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + LS_item * group + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + group * LS_item + Constr * LS_item + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
##
##                               npar    AIC    BIC
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_LS                6 2886.3 2922.7
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS            7 2879.8 2922.3
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS_group_int  8 2879.4 2927.9
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int  9 2880.0 2934.6
##
##                               logLik deviance
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_LS                -1437.1  2874.3
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS            -1432.9  2865.8
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS_group_int  -1431.7  2863.4
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int -1431.0  2862.0
##
##                               Chisq Df
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_LS                8.4315  1
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS            2.4900  1
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS_group_int  1.3633  1
##
##                               Pr(>Chisq)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_LS                0.003688 **
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS            0.114573
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS_group_int  0.242959
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```

anova(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS,SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int)

```

```
## Data: data_SI_core
## Models:
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + LS_item + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int: gram_in_core_binom ~ group * Constr + group * LS_item + Constr * LS_item + (1 | child) + (1 | item)
##
## npar AIC BIC
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS 7 2879.8 2922.3
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int 9 2880.0 2934.6
## logLik deviance
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS -1432.9 2865.8
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int -1431.0 2862.0
## Chisq Df
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int 3.8533 2
## Pr(>Chisq)
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS
## SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_group_LS_int_Constr_LS_int 0.1456
```

```
print(Anova_SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS <- Anova(SI_gram_in_core_Constr_group_int_LS, type="II"))
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald chisquare tests)
##
## Response: gram_in_core_binom
## Chisq Df Pr(>Chisq)
## group 16.1099 1 5.977e-05 ***
## Constr 14.5480 1 0.0001366 ***
## LS_item 9.7733 1 0.0017706 **
## group:Constr 8.6056 1 0.0033514 **
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Vyhýbací strategie a chyby v produkci cílových struktur

Vyhýbací strategie u cílových vztažných vět

Opakování vět

```

data <- data.frame(
  skupina = c("děti s VD", "děti s TJV"),
  "NotAnswer" = c(21,57),
  "OtherOmit" = c(666,398),
  "AnotherGramStruct" = c(497,267),
  "AnotherWhStruct" = c(405,431),
  "TargWhStruct" = c(427,863)
)

data <- data %>%
  rename(`Cílový typ vztažné věty` = TargWhStruct,
         `Jiný typ vztažné věty` = AnotherWhStruct,
         `Jiná gramatická struktura` = AnotherGramStruct,
         `Jiná agramatická struktura` = OtherOmit,
         `Nezodpovězeno` = NotAnswer
  )

data_long <- pivot_longer(data,
                          cols = `Cílový typ vztažné věty`:`Nezodpovězeno`,
                          names_to = "Použitá struktura",
                          values_to = "Celkový počet")

data_long <- data_long %>%
  group_by(skupina) %>%
  mutate(procenta = `Celkový počet` / sum(`Celkový počet`) * 100)

data_long$skupina <- factor(data_long$skupina, levels = c("děti s VD", "děti s TJV"))

data_long$`Použitá struktura` <- factor(data_long$`Použitá struktura`,
                                       levels = c("Cílový typ vztažné věty",
                                                  "Jiný typ vztažné věty",
                                                  "Jiná gramatická struktura",
                                                  "Jiná agramatická struktura",
                                                  "Nezodpovězeno"))

ggplot(data_long, aes(x = skupina, y = procenta, fill = `Použitá struktura`)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "stack") +
  geom_text(aes(label = sprintf("%.0f%%", procenta),
                position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5), size = 3) +
  labs(x = "Skupina", title = "Použití cílových vztažných vět a vyhýbacích strategií") +
  theme_minimal() +
  scale_y_continuous(labels = scales::percent_format(scale = 1), breaks = seq(0, 100, by = 10)) +
  scale_fill_brewer(palette = "Set3")

```

Použití cílových vztahných vět a vyhýbacích strategií

Elicitovaná produkce

```

data <- data.frame(
  skupina = c("děti s VD", "děti s TJV"),
  "WhStruct" = c(463,680),
  "AnotherGramStruct" = c(123,86),
  "OtherOmit" = c(329,174),
  "repetition" = c(46,37),
  "NotAnswer" = c(21,16)
)

data <- data %>%
  rename(`Vztažná věta` = WhStruct,
         `Jiná gramatická struktura` = AnotherGramStruct,
         `Jiná agramatická struktura` = OtherOmit,
         `Zopakování úvodní věty` = repetition,
         `Nezodpovězeno` = NotAnswer
  )

data_long <- pivot_longer(data,
                          cols = `Vztažná věta`:`Nezodpovězeno`,
                          names_to = "Použitá struktura",
                          values_to = "Celkový počet")

data_long <- data_long %>%
  group_by(skupina) %>%
  mutate(procenta = `Celkový počet` / sum(`Celkový počet`) * 100)

data_long$skupina <- factor(data_long$skupina, levels = c("děti s VD", "děti s TJV"))

data_long$`Použitá struktura` <- factor(data_long$`Použitá struktura`,
                                       levels = c("Vztažná věta",
                                                  "Jiná gramatická struktura",
                                                  "Jiná agramatická struktura",
                                                  "Zopakování úvodní věty",
                                                  "Nezodpovězeno"))

ggplot(data_long, aes(x = skupina, y = procenta, fill = `Použitá struktura`)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "stack") +
  geom_text(aes(label = sprintf("%.0f%%", procenta)),
            position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5), size = 3) +
  labs(x = "Skupina", title = "Použití vztažných vět a vyhýbacích strategií") +
  theme_minimal() +
  scale_y_continuous(labels = scales::percent_format(scale = 1), breaks = seq(0, 100, by = 10)) +
  scale_fill_brewer(palette = "Set3")

```

Použití vztažných vět a vyhýbacích strategií

Vyhýbací strategie u cílových nominálních frází s

adjektivem

Opakování vět

```
data <- data.frame(
  skupina = c("děti s VD", "děti s TJV"),
  "TargAdjPhr" = c(445,623),
  "WhStruct" = c(29,22),
  "AnotherGramStruct" = c(187,146),
  "OtherOmit" = c(337,198),
  "NotAnswer" = c(8,19)
)

data <- data %>%
  rename(`Nominální fráze s adjektivem` = TargAdjPhr,
         `Vztažná struktura` = WhStruct,
         `Jiná gramatická struktura` = AnotherGramStruct,
         `Jiná agramatická struktura` = OtherOmit,
         `Nezodpovězeno` = NotAnswer
  )

data_long <- pivot_longer(data,
                          cols = `Nominální fráze s adjektivem`:`Nezodpovězeno`,
                          names_to = "Použitá struktura",
                          values_to = "Celkový počet")

data_long <- data_long %>%
  group_by(skupina) %>%
  mutate(procenta = `Celkový počet` / sum(`Celkový počet`) * 100)

data_long$skupina <- factor(data_long$skupina, levels = c("děti s VD", "děti s TJV"))

data_long$`Použitá struktura` <- factor(data_long$`Použitá struktura`,
                                       levels = c("Nominální fráze s adjektivem",
                                                  "Vztažná struktura",
                                                  "Jiná gramatická struktura",
                                                  "Jiná agramatická struktura",
                                                  "Nezodpovězeno"))

ggplot(data_long, aes(x = skupina, y = procenta, fill = `Použitá struktura`)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "stack") +
  geom_text(aes(label = sprintf("%.0f%%", procenta),
                position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5), size = 3) +
            labs(x = "Skupina", title = "Použití cílových nominálních frází s adjektivem a vyhýbacích
strategií") +
            theme_minimal() +
            scale_y_continuous(labels = scales::percent_format(scale = 1), breaks = seq(0, 100, by = 1
0)) +
            scale_fill_brewer(palette = "Set3")
```

Použití cílových nominálních frází s adjektivem a vyhýbacích strategií

Elicitovaná produkce

```

data <- data.frame(
  skupina = c("děti s VD", "děti s TJV"),
  "TargAdj" = c(639,773),
  "SentAdj" = c(31,34),
  "AnotherGramStruct" = c(65,52),
  "OtherOmit" = c(145,60),
  "repetition" = c(36,39),
  "NotAnswer" = c(7,3)
)

data <- data %>%
  rename(`Cílová nominální fráze s adjektivem` = TargAdj,
         `Nominální fráze s adjektivem ve větě` = SentAdj,
         `Jiná gramatická struktura` = AnotherGramStruct,
         `Jiná agramatická struktura` = OtherOmit,
         `Zopakování úvodní věty` = repetition,
         `Nezodpovězeno` = NotAnswer
  )

data_long <- pivot_longer(data,
                          cols = `Cílová nominální fráze s adjektivem`:`Nezodpovězeno`,
                          names_to = "Použitá struktura",
                          values_to = "Celkový počet")

data_long <- data_long %>%
  group_by(skupina) %>%
  mutate(procenta = `Celkový počet` / sum(`Celkový počet`) * 100)

data_long$skupina <- factor(data_long$skupina, levels = c("děti s VD", "děti s TJV"))

data_long$`Použitá struktura` <- factor(data_long$`Použitá struktura`,
                                       levels = c("Cílová nominální fráze s adjektivem",
                                                  "Nominální fráze s adjektivem ve větě",
                                                  "Jiná gramatická struktura",
                                                  "Jiná agramatická struktura",
                                                  "Zopakování úvodní věty",
                                                  "Nezodpovězeno"))

ggplot(data_long, aes(x = skupina, y = procenta, fill = `Použitá struktura`)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "stack") +
  geom_text(aes(label = sprintf("%.0f%%", procenta)),
            position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5), size = 3) +
  labs(x = "Skupina", title = "Použití cílových nominálních frází s adjektivem a vyhýbacích
strategií") +
  theme_minimal() +
  scale_y_continuous(labels = scales::percent_format(scale = 1), breaks = seq(0, 100, by = 1
0)) +
  scale_fill_brewer(palette = "Set3")

```

Použití cílových nominálních frází s adjektivem a vyhýbacích strategií

